

D11.1: Project Handbook

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036388

Disclaimer

The content of this document reflects only the author's view. Neither the European Commission nor REA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the ZEROW consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the ZEROW Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the ZEROW Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© ZEROW Consortium. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Acronym ZeroW **Grant Agreement No** 101036388

Full Title	Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain - ZeroW		
Call	H2020-LC-GD-2020 Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal.		
Topic	LC-GD-6-1-2020	Type of action	IA
Project coordinator	Inlecom Commercial Pathways		
Project URL	http://www.zerow-project.eu/		
Deliverable	D11.1 Project Handbook		
Document Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead beneficiary	Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP)		
Responsible author	Anna George (ICP)		
Additional authors and contributors	Dusan Drabik (WU), Frank Berkers (TNO), Jovana Vlaskalin (BIOS), Debolina Paul (DIGI), Isabeau Coopmans (ILVO), Kata Trifkovic (ICP), Angèle Tasse (ICLEI), Louise Krogh Johnson (FBCD), Jenny Rainbird (ICP)		
Due date of delivery	28/02/2022	Submission date	28/02/2022

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V0.1	07/01/2022	Template and document structure completed	AG (ICP)
V0.2	14/01/2022	Chapter 2 - completed	AG (ICP)
V0.3	28/01/2022	Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 - completed	AG (ICP)
V1.0	23/02/2022	First draft of document – reviewed	JR (ICP)
V1.1	23/02/2022	Comments and contributions in Chapter 3 – Project Management Plan, Delivery plan for: WP2	FB (TNO)
		WP9	AT (ICLEI)
	24/02/2021	WP5	DP (DIGI)
		WP10	LKJ (FBCD)
		WP4	JV (BIOS)
		WP6	IC (ILVO)
V2.0	28/02/2022	Comments addressing and document finalisation	AG (ICP)
V3.0	30/11/2023	Inclusion of conflict resolution procedure and clarification of the role of the Gender Manager	AG (ICP)

Reviewed by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
V1.0	23/02/2022	Jenny Rainbird	ICP
V3.0	10/12/2023	Zacharoula Papamitsiou	SINTEF

Contents

1. Introduction	11
Mapping ZeroW outputs	13
Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	16
2. Project Governance	17
ZeroW Governance structure overview	17
Council of Partners	19
Project Steering Group	20
Project Coordinator	25
EC Project Officer	26
External Advisory Board	26
Innovation Management Board	28
All Partners	29
3. Project Management Plan	29
Project delivery plan	30
WP1 Modelling FLW economics from F2F	30
WP2 OFLW Data Space	33
WP3 ZEROW Systemic Innovation Support Tools to assist developers design and implement SIC support applications	37
WP4 Systemic Innovation demonstration	40
WP5 Systemic Innovation assessment	45
WP6 Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero FLW	48
WP7 Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs	51
WP8 Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW	55
WP9 Cooperation with EC services & other projects/initiatives	58
WP10 Dissemination & communication	61
WP11 Project management	63
Monitoring and control of project work	65
Milestones	66
Periodic progress monitoring	66
4. Quality Management Plan	69
Quality Assurance Procedure	69
ZeroW Deliverable Quality Review Schedule	72
5. Risk Management Plan	72
Risk management process	73
Risk Reporting: ZeroW Risk register	76
Risk Treatment	76
6. Communications Management Plan	77
Contact list and maintenance	77
Project Meetings Calendar	78
Mailing lists	78
ZeroW Partners Newsletter (Internal newsletter)	78
Collaborative workspace – ZeroW Project MS Teams Area	79
Conflicts resolution	86
7. Stakeholder Management Plan	88
8. Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart	89
9. Annex II: Guide for reporting of D&C activities	90
10. Annex III: Conflict Resolution Record Document Template	93

List of figures

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance.....	11
Figure 2 ZeroW Consortium bodies as per CA article 6.1	18
Figure 3 ZeroW Governance Structure	19
Figure 4 Innovation Management Board composition – Clusters, organisations, relevant SILLs	28
Figure 5 WP1: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	31
Figure 6 WP2: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	33
Figure 7 WP3: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	37
Figure 8 WP4: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	41
Figure 9 WP4: SILLs Partners and roles	43
Figure 10 WP5: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	46
Figure 11 WP6: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies	48
Figure 12 WP7: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	51
Figure 13 WP8: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	56
Figure 14 WP9: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.	58
Figure 15 Relationship between WP9 and WP19 scope and delivery	59
Figure 16 ZeroW Quality assurance process steps.....	69
Figure 17 FERMA Risk Management Standard	73
Figure 18 ZeroW Project Teams Area	79
Figure 19 MS Teams view: New post in Channel WP11 as seen by all Team members	80
Figure 20 MS Teams view: Notification for new post mention, as seen by the Teams member that is mentioned or tagged in a post	81
Figure 21 Notification view in the Activity tab	81
Figure 22 System limitation for auto-show channels in a team.....	82
Figure 23 Unhide channels	82

List of tables

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used	8
Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description	13
Table 3 Project Steering Group members and role description	23
Table 4 External Advisory Board Members	27
Table 5 WP1 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project	31
Table 6 WP1: RACI Matrix and efforts per task.....	32
Table 7 WP1: Deliverables list.....	32
Table 8 WP2 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project	34
Table 9 WP2: RACI Matrix and efforts per task.....	35
Table 10 WP2: Deliverables list.....	36
Table 11 WP3 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project	38
Table 12 WP3: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	39
Table 13 WP3: Deliverables list.....	40
Table 14 WP4 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project	41
Table 15 WP4: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	42

Table 16 WP4: Deliverables list.....	44
Table 17 SILLs main outputs.....	45
Table 18 WP5 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project.....	46
Table 19 WP5: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	47
Table 20 WP5: Deliverables list.....	47
Table 21 WP6 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project.....	49
Table 22 WP6: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	49
Table 23 WP6: Deliverables list.....	50
Table 24 WP7 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project.....	51
Table 25 WP7: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	53
Table 26 WP7: Deliverables list.....	54
Table 27 WP8 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project.....	56
Table 28 WP8: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	57
Table 29 WP8: Deliverables list.....	57
Table 30 WP9 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project.....	58
Table 31 WP9: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	60
Table 32 WP9: Deliverables list.....	61
Table 33 WP10: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	62
Table 34 WP10: Deliverables list.....	63
Table 35 WP11: RACI Matrix and efforts per task	64
Table 36 WP11: Deliverables list.....	64
Table 37 ZeroW Milestones.....	66
Table 38 Example of Deliverable quality and implementation plan	69
Table 39 Preview of ZeroW deliverables quality review schedule	72
Table 40 Risk Register: structured description of risk	74
Table 41 Risk evaluation matrix	75
Table 42 Conflict resolution process steps.....	87
Table 43 Performace issues resolution steps.....	88

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
AFL	Agrifood DIH Lithuania
ALDELIS	Aves Nobles y Derivados, S.L.
ALL	Allmicroalgae Natural Products
ART21	ART21
ASINCAR	Asociación de Investigación de Industrias Cárnicas del Principado de Asturias
ATC	Agro Transilvania Cluster
ATIT	Asociatia Transilvania IT - Transilvanian DIH
BIOS	BioSense Insitute
CA	Consortium Agreement
CM	Commercialisation Manager
CoP	Council of Partners
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DIGI	Digiotouch OU
DIL	Deutsches Institut für Lebensmitteltechnik e.V.
DM	Dissemination Manager
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EGM	Ethics and Gender-issues Manager
EROSKI	Eroski S. Coop.
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
F6S	F6S Network Ireland Ltd
FBCD	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
FCTA	Fundación Corporación Tecnológica Andaluza
FERMA	Federation of the European Risk Management Associations
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
GLC	Grupo La Caña
I&CB	Innovation and Commercialisation Board
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems - NTUA
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH (ICLEI ES)
ICP	Inlecom Commercial Pathways
IFAPA	Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria y Pesquera
ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
ISP	Innovatiesteunpunt voor landbouw en platteland

ITA	Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón
ITC	Innovation Technology Cluster Murska Subota / DIH AGROFOOD
ITENE	Instituto Tecnológico del Embalaje, Transporte y Logística ITENE
ITL	Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation
KGZS	Institute of Agriculture and Forestry Murska Sobota
KNT	Konnecta Systems
LM	Liaison Manager
LVPA	Lithuanian Vegetable Producers Association
MST	Multiscan
NVMNT	Novamont S.p.A.
OVAM	OVAM - Public Waste Agency of Flanders
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
PSG	Project Steering Group
RAG	Red/Amber/Green colour scheme
REA	European Research Executive Agency
ROBIN	Robin Food
SAFE	SAFE Safe Food Advocacy Europe A.S.B.L.
SFC	LITMEA (Smart Food Cluster)
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SILLC	SILLs Coordinator
SIM	Systemic Innovation Manager
SINTEF	SINTEF
SONAE	SONAE
SVZ	S.V.Z International B.V. - Royal Cosun Group
TERMO	Termoformas de Levante S.L.
TIU	Stichting Katholieke Universiteit Brabant – Tilburg University
TNO	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek
TSG	Technical Steering Group
UM	University Maribor
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
VBL	Voedselbank Limburg vzw
VLTN	VLTN
WIT	Waterford Institute of Technology - TSSG
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders
WU	Wageningen University & Research

Executive summary

The ZeroW Project Handbook presents the main rules and approaches for inter-project coordination. It is designed as a useful reference tool to be used by the Partners when they need information about how the Project work is organised, including the governance (decision authority levels), roles and responsibilities, input/output dependencies between tasks, timelines and deliverables, reporting, monitoring and control of project execution.

The document also describes the processes to be implemented by all Partners for quality control and risk management.

Finally, a large proportion of the document is dedicated to setting up efficient communications between the 46 ZeroW Partners to foster collaboration as the recognised important factor for successful project delivery. A detailed description and guidance for the use of the Collaborative workspace is also included to help Partners to easily navigate through the project information and documentation.

1. Introduction

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system (Figure 1).

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The approach involves:

- (i) pre-identifying systemic innovations, that incorporate multiple interlinked dimensions (process, organisational, strategy, marketing, product, technological, governance, etc.), which are tested and demonstrated;
- (ii) steering the evolution of innovations towards higher levels of systemic readiness and impact, using a Living Lab co-creation and multi-actor collective learning approach;
- (iii) enhancing the Living Lab actors' innovation advancement capability with shared resources facilitating new ways and means of cooperating and co-developing innovations;
- (iv) developing context-specific trajectories for the systemic innovations (from ideation to scaling-up and commercialisation) leading to the provision of currently missing end products and services that align with consumer attitudes, food actor needs and policy trends. Moreover, ZeroW establishes a clear 'FLW impact trajectory', from demonstrator

results (2025), scaled up to meet the F2F 2030 goals, and steered through a 'just transition pathway' towards a near-zero FLW in 2050.

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables. This document is originating from WP11, Project Management. **The objective of this deliverable is to define the main rules, conventions and approaches to be used by the partners for administration tasks, project management, deliverable preparation & assessment, communication and inter-project coordination.**

Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D11.1 Project Handbook	Project Handbook - Will present the main rules and approaches for inter-project coordination.	Entire document	The Handbook is designed as a reference tool to be used by Partners to find information regarding the project governance, project management plan, quality and risk management procedures, organisation of the internal communication to facilitate the efficient project work coordination and successful achievement of the project objectives.
TASKS			
T11.1 Administrative and financial management	This Task will undertake the monitoring, control and execution of all administrative and financial aspects of the project, guaranteeing the adherence of the project work to the schedule, resources and plan. The following work items are included in this Task:		
	(i) developing a Project Handbook, defining the main rules, conventions and approaches to be used by the partners for administration tasks,	Chapter 2 Project Governance	Provides guidance on the governance structure of the project, the decision-making process

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	project management,	Chapter 3 Project Management Plan	Provides detailed information on the project delivery on WP level, including objectives, dependencies between WPs and tasks, roles and responsibilities of partners, main outputs to be delivered. Describes the approach to the monitoring and control of the project work.
		Chapter 5 Risk Management Plan	Describes the ZeroW process for risk management to ensure the successful delivery of the project by avoiding or reducing possible negative impacts on the work and maximising the opportunities which could make the work more efficient and effective.
	deliverable preparation & assessment,	Chapter 4 Quality Management Plan	Provides description of the deliverable preparation and quality control process embedded in it.
	communication and inter-project coordination;	Chapter 6 Communications Management Plan	Defines the main rules, conventions and approaches to be used regarding the internal project communication, including contact list and its maintenance, project meetings calendar set-up, internal project mailing lists and newsletter, project collaborative workspace and its use.

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	(ii) ensuring the consistency between project work plan and financial guidelines;	Not part of scope of current deliverable	
	(iii) producing, compiling, monitoring and analysing periodical reports and management/final reports for the EC;		
	(iv) ensuring the Consortium payments in accordance with budget consumption;		
	(v) dealing with legal issues that may occur i.e. contracts, contract amendments etc.;		
	(vi) executing all payments of the project;		
	(viii) managing the processes of project reviews.		
	(vii) undertaking the liaison with all partners regarding their administrative and financial obligations;		

Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The ZeroW project handbook structure and outline of the respective chapters is summarised below:

- Chapter 1 Introduction
 - includes overview of the deliverable mapping against the work package and task requirements, handbook structure.
- Chapter 2 Project Governance
 - provides an overview of ZeroW project governance and project management structure: project bodies and their authorities, individual members and their roles and responsibilities.
- Chapter 3 Project Management Plan
 - provides clarity of scope, roles, timelines and to foster collaboration through highlighting early in the project the input/output task dependencies and stimulate the information exchange between the respective delivery parties. The project delivery plan for each WP includes information on objectives, interoperability, roles and responsibilities, main outputs.
- Chapter 4 Quality Management Plan
 - here you will find the description of the quality assurance process embedded in ZeroW project delivery to underpin the production of relevant and high-quality project outputs.
- Chapter 5 Risk Management Plan
 - provides the description of the step-by-step Risk Management process to be implemented in ZeroW project, based on the requirements of the FERMA Standard.
- Chapter 6 Communications Management Plan
 - here you will find information about the management of the internal communication between the Partners during the delivery of the project to support a smooth and flowless collaboration between the large number of the ZeroW delivering organisations.
- Chapter 7 Stakeholder Management Plan
 - links with deliverable D9.1 Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement.
- The Annexes include the ZeroW detailed Gantt Chart and the guide for reporting of Dissemination and communication activities and the template for the Conflict Resolution Record Document.

2. Project Governance

In this section

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of ZeroW project governance and project management structure: project bodies and their authorities, individual members and their roles and responsibilities.

ZeroW Governance structure overview

The ZeroW governance represents the project decision making process structure, designed to enable the successful delivery of the project and achieving its objectives and contractual obligations. It is designed to support straightforward authority levels for decision making, including issues and conflict resolution if/when they arise. The project governance structure outlined below provides for clear procedures for decision making and accountability and well-defined roles and responsibilities related to the governance including transparent communication and information dissemination both intra-project and with REA.

The governance structure is tailored to meet the ZeroW projects specifics. The large consortium of 46 partners and 3 linked parties, requires a multi-level communication system to provide quick and efficient communication and reduce the risks of silo working due to participation of partners in specific technical areas of the project. Additionally, the diverse technical and practical knowledge represented in the individual work packages, necessitates tight communication links between them to ensure the proper technical/scientific guidance and steering of the project. Thus, crucial to the successful organisation and coordination of the project delivery work are the good understanding of individual roles and responsibilities, the clear decision-making structure and the mechanisms for continuous monitoring and control.

The project management structure of ZeroW supports the high-quality research and innovation required to find solutions of the structural and behavioural lock-in effects and lead to sustainable reduction of the Food Loss and Waste (FLW) and medium and long term. The project is structured around a large number of Living Labs supporting systemic innovations in various domains of the food supply chain and involving multiple internal and external stakeholders. The coordination of their activities with the rest of the technical and impact orientated workstreams is integral factor for the success of the systemic innovations and capacity building objectives.

Finally, the project governance structure encompasses the required guidance, calibration and validation of the project results provided by important external to the project groups of stakeholders through the embedded involvement of the External Advisory Board.

Figure 2 ZeroW Consortium bodies as per CA article 6.1

According to the ZeroW Consortium Agreement (CA), the organisational structure of the Consortium consist of the following bodies, depicted in Figure 2:

- Project *Council of Partners* (CoP)
- *Project Steering Group* (PSG)
- *External Advisory Board* (EAB)
- *Project Coordinator* (PC)

In addition to the bodies described in the CA, the GA Part B (2.2.3.1 Commercialisation strategy) refers to *Innovation Management Board* which will report directly to the Council of Partners (CoP).

Finally, a Technical Steering Group (TSG) was created in implementation of Task 11.2 Technical Coordination, quality control and risk management. The TSG has an advisory role to the PC and the PSG.

This complete project governance structure is presented in *Figure 3* below.

Figure 3 ZeroW Governance Structure

Council of Partners

The project Council of Partners (CoP) is the **ultimate decision-making body** of the ZeroW Consortium. It is composed by one representative of each ZeroW Partner (CA 6.3.1.1.1). The CoP is chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC).

The CoP has the sole authority to make decision regarding changes in the project plan, content, finances and intellectual property rights. All proposals for changes in Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement (GA) have to be approved by the CoP prior to submission for approval by REA.

Any decisions with regards to modifications to Attachment 1 of CA (Background Included), Attachment 3 of CA (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to CA Section 8.3.2) and Attachment 4 of CA (Identified Affiliated Entities) as well as ones regarding the evolution of the ZeroW Consortium should be made by the CoP. The procedures for CoP decision making are detailed in the Consortium Agreement. It also captures the meeting set-up, voting and veto processes.

Project Steering Group

The PSG is the **supervisory body for the project execution** and is responsible for the day-to-day management of ZeroW. It reports to and is accountable to the Project Council of Partners.

The PSG is composed by a team of experts responsible for the monitoring of the effective and efficient implementation of the project. Its **responsibilities** are:

- To collect information quarterly¹ on the progress of the Project, examines it to assess the compliance of the actual delivery with the project plan and, if necessary, proposes corrective actions or modifications of the project plan to the CoP.
- To support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Funding Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables.
- To prepare the CoP meetings, proposes decisions and prepares the agenda for those meetings and is responsible for the execution and implementation of the decisions of the CoP.
- to prepare the content and timing of the press releases and joint Consortium publications in execution of article 29 of the GA.

The GA requires the PSG to hold **virtual meetings on a bi-weekly interval**, and additionally – upon an issue or request. It is interpreted by the PSG members as a requirement for the starting period of the project where such a frequency is required to synchronise the work between all the WPs, after which the frequency of the meetings can be decreased. The CA stipulates that those should be held at least on quarterly basis.

To support the Coordinator and the PSG with the everyday delivery and technical decision making the ZeroW project has set up working groups, which may convene ad-hoc at their own discretion in the periods in between the formal PSG meetings to allow for more efficient decision making in the specific competencies areas. If the matter of discussions however falls within the PSG authority, then the respective WG should present the problem and the proposed solution to the PSG for approval. The WG meetings can be convened by request of any of its members.

Technical Working Group

The Technical WG is composed by the WP leads of WP1-4, the Systemic Innovation Manager and the SILLs Coordinator. The objective of the set-up of this WG is to provide a medium for quick information exchange and respectively – faster decision making between the WPs delivering the Data space, the Systemic innovation support tools, the Demonstrations and the FLW Modelling. The dependencies between those

¹ As per Annex 2 Part B of GA, section 3.2.1.2. CA article 6.3.2.3.5 requires this to happen at least every 6 months.

WPs are critical for the successful delivery of the project and the Technical WG can convene and discuss when the need arises, without having to involve the entire PSG.

Impact Working Group

The Impact WG is composed by the WP leads of WP5-8 and the Commercialisation Manager. The objective of the set-up of this WG is to provide a medium for quick information exchange and respectively – faster decision making between the WPs assessing and amplifying the impact of the project through capacity building, innovation fostering and sustainable commercial exploitation of the results.

The Technical WG and the Impact WG, together with the Project Technical Lead and the Commercial Application Advisor, compose the Technical Steering Group (TSG), which supports the Coordinator with the Technical, Quality and Risk management of the project in an advisory role.

Communication Working Group

The Communication WG is composed by the WP leads of WP9 and WP10, the Dissemination Manager and the Liaison Manager. The objective of the set-up of this WG is to provide a medium for quick information exchange and respectively – faster decision making between the WPs responsible for the external project communication, dissemination and strategic cooperation and synergies identification with other projects and EC initiatives. The scope of work of WP9 and WP 10 is strongly related and interdependent as clarified in Chapter 3 Project Management Plan

.

Management and Compliance Working Group

The Management and Compliance WG is composed by the Project Coordinator and the Ethics and Gender Manager and is set up to provide a medium for quick information exchange and respectively – faster decision making in the area of ethics, GDPR compliance and gender equality and the efficient implementation across the entire project.

Additionally, the role of the Gender manager is to address and follow up on any queries raised from the partners working on the "Cluster-, place-, context- & actor-based consolidation & interpretation of results" (T5.3) with regards to gender aspects of the research.

Detailed description of PSG procedures is included in the CA. It captures the meeting set-up, decision making, voting and veto processes.

The composition of the PSG and the contacts of its members is given in the table below. The roles and responsibilities are also listed, based on the respective definitions in the GA.

Table 3 Project Steering Group members and role description

Role	Partner	Contact	Role description
Project Coordinator and WP7 and WP11 Lead	ICP	Anna George (Kata Trifkovic)	It is discussed in detail in the Project Coordinator section below.
WP1 Lead	WU	Dusan Drabik	Role: Leader of a given Work Package reports on the progress of the WP to the PC and TC. Tasks: Produces detailed progress reports. Manages the timely and effective execution of the WP/task work. Ensures deliverables meet the quality standards. Represents WPs at the PSG. Monitors and guides task developments in close cooperation with the task Leaders.
WP2 Lead	TNO	Frank Berkers	
WP3 Lead	WIT	Paul Malone	
WP4 Lead	BIOS	Stavros Tsitouras	
WP5 Lead	DIGI	Debolina Paul	
WP6 Lead	ILVO	Isabeau Coopmans	
WP8 Lead	SAFE	Antoine D'haese	
WP9 Lead	ICLEI	Angèle Tasse	
WP10 Lead	FBCD	Heidi G. Hoy Dyrholm	
Systemic Innovation Manager (SIM)	TNO	Frank Berkers	
SILLs Coordinator (SILLC)	BIOS	Milica Trajkovic	Role: Monitors the implementation of the SILLs, the achievement of the KPIs and the alignment of the SILLs with the horizontal WPs, together with the TC, and with the systemic innovation approach, together with the SIM. Tasks: Monitors SILL KPIs, systemic innovation alignment and technical progress.
Dissemination Manager (DM)	FBCD	Louise Krogh Johnson	Role: DM will be responsible for ensuring that all dissemination and communication activities of the project are well directed, of good quality and relevant to the target audiences. Tasks: Set a clear and suitable dissemination and communication strategy and

Role	Partner	Contact	Role description
			monitor its implementation together with ZeroW consortium. The DM will report directly to the PC.
Commercialisation Manager (CM)	ICP	Kata Trifkovic (Patrick Durkin)	Role: Instils the commercial impact and impetus to the technical solutions developed in ZeroW with a view to evidencing commercial advantages for the project's technology provider, bringing this perspective in to PSG decisions and supporting partners with exploitation activities. Tasks: Specifies Value Propositions and maintains the business/commercialisation strategy and supports impact maximisation for the project outputs to the EU agrifood sector. Pays attention to discerning IPR at regular checkpoints and organising patents filing to protect commercial advantages 'within and outside Europe' and 'for Europe'.
Liaison Manager (LM)	ICLEI	Peter Defranceschi	Role: advise and monitor international collaboration both from policy, technical and social aspects for accelerated progress towards ZeroW objectives on FLW reduction. Plan and execute the liaison activities described in WP9 to engage relevant stakeholders along the project execution. Reports to CoP. Tasks: in strong collaboration with PC, CM and DM, supports the ZeroW consortium to identify international trends and engage with other stakeholders and activities related to the project.
Ethics and Gender-issues Manager (EGM)	SINTEF	Hans Torvatn	Role: supervise that ZeroW follows the guidelines of the Commission regarding ethics and gender-issues management in research and innovations activities, especially those regarding the handling of personal or sensitive data. Tasks: monitor and self-assess, in collaboration with the PC, that the data gathered in the project do not imply critical ethical issues. This task will be included in the DMP.

Project Coordinator

The role of the Project Coordinator (PC) in ZeroW is assumed by ICP. The PC has the overall responsibility for the management of the project and for the official communication with the EC being the intermediary between the project governance bodies and the Funding Authority (REA).

The PC has the following responsibilities, listed in article 6.4.2 of the CA:

- Monitoring Partners compliance with their contractual obligations and the project plan delivery;
- Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting project deliverables and other document, required by the Project Officer (PO).
- Transmitting official communication and project documentation to Partners. Providing official copies or originals of documents that are in possession of the PC, when such are required by Partners to present claims.
- Administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.3 of the CA.
- Updating and providing access to the contact list of the Members and other contact persons.

Furthermore, the PC chairs the CoP and the PSG and is responsible for sharing the written minutes of each CoP and PSG meeting to all Members.

The PC is supported in the organisation and delivery of the ZeroW project management by the PSG.

Additionally, the PC has responsibilities in relation to the EAB:

- ensuring NDAs have been signed between each of the EAB members and all the Partners in ZeroW Consortium.
- Prepare the minutes of meeting for the EAB meetings.
- Prepare the implementation of the EAB suggestions, following the project governance procedures.

The GA provides additional requirements to the PC:

- Perform risk assessment in collaboration with PSG members and implementation of mitigation measures
- Ensure high-quality deliverables and fully tested solutions.
- Produce agenda and minutes for the PSG and CoP meetings.
- Manage the information flows between partners.
- Organise resolution procedures of consortium issues.
- In the event of an unexpected results or underperformance, flag the issue to the CoP, that will determine the appropriate course of action.

The following tasks the PC executes with the support and under the guidance and advice of the appointed by the PSG project **Technical Lead**:

- Align technical direction with systemic innovation management to maintain ZeroW systemic innovation character.
- Provide technical vision regarding the ZeroW developed solutions, and how it advances the state of the art in the direction of agri-food industry requirements.
- Support technical decisions by the PSG by setting the technical agenda and monitoring technical outputs.
- Provide clear project vision in collaboration with PSG and EAB and ensure final reports submitted to the EU are complete and accurate.

The project Technical Lead participates in the PSG meetings and provides technical/scientific guidance to steer the project to keep its designated course and achieve its objectives. The project Technical Lead does not have a voting right in the PSG.

EC Project Officer

REA monitors and controls the GA execution during the project delivery through the assigned Project Officer (PO). Her role includes monitoring the timely project deliverables submission via the Participants Portal, reviewing the Periodic project reports and participating in the periodic project reviews.

Additionally, the PO monitors the achieving of the project objectives versus the planned ones, controls the project financial aspects and the contractual obligation fulfilment and participates in the process for amending of the GA, reviewing the suggested changes and if acceptable – forwarding them for additional review and approval of the EC services.

External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board (EAB) is appointed by the PSG. Its **role** as described in the CA is to “assist and facilitate the decisions made by the Project Council of Partners”. The role and composition are also discussed in the GA, section 3.2.1.1:

“The EAB will offer impartial scientific advice, support the PSG and advise the consortium on social, environmental, technological, legal and economic factors that may influence the innovation management of ZeroW. It will be chaired by one of its members, elected upon the EAB’s first meeting in M1. The EAB comprises a gender-balanced group of external advisors representing FLW innovation disruptors, FLW innovation enablers, innovation financial supporter and investors, among others.”

During the proposal development, the following organisations have provided letters of support, confirming their interest to participate in ZeroW in a quality of **EAB member**:

Table 4 External Advisory Board Members

Name	Details
Judith Ketelslegers	CEO of Foresightee , organisation who forecasts sales of fresh food, striving towards the reduction of FLW.
Anne-Charlotte Mornington	Head of Partnerships and Special Projects and Founding member of OLIO , a free food sharing app, with extensive experience in the field of food waste.
Piotr Barczak	Senior Waste Policy Officer of EEB, European Environmental Bureau , working on an EU level in the process of revision of food waste directives.
Pierre Condamine	Waste Policy Officer of Zero Waste Europe , lobbying for an ambitious legislative framework on food waste reduction at the EU level.
Thinagaran Perumal	Associate Professor at the Department for Computer Science in the Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology at the University of Putra Malaysia , with extensive expertise in agri-tech and IoT applied to the agrifood sector.
Markus Hurschler	Managing Partner of Foodways Consulting GmbH , who develops tools and methodologies for food waste reduction.
Ricardo Monagas	CTO at TotalCtrl AS , who helps food banks, municipalities, households and restaurants to prevent food waste with software solutions.
Patrick Fransen	Partner at Pebble Wave , an incubator, investor and private equity fund for purpose-driven organisations.
Koen Tahon	Relationship Manager and Innovation Banker at ING Belgium , who offers financing solutions for family-owned companies related to food industry & agriculture.

New members can be appointed through a PSG decision providing there are no objections of any partner.

The **EAB meetings** will be convened annually at the same time with CoP meetings. The members with specific expertise are also permitted to participate upon invitation in the CoP's and PSG meetings, however they have only consultancy and advisory role and no voting rights.

There is a specific **budget** allocated to the PC for EAB allowances for travel and hotel with the amount of €5,900.

The CA also has a requirement with regards to the **exchange of confidential information** between the EAB members and the Consortium members. Each EAB member must sign an NDA with all Consortium Partners. The signature should happen before any confidential information is exchanged or no later than 30 calendar days after their nomination. The clauses in the NDA with the EAB members should not be more favourable (i.e. “less stringent”) than the confidentiality clauses in the CA.

Innovation Management Board

The GA envisages the set-up of an Innovation Management Board that is composed by the Commercialisation Manager (CM), and appointed leaders of the following SILLs clusters:

- IT Platform;
- Pre- and post-harvest innovations;
- Food processing innovations;
- Wholesale, Retail and Consumer innovations.

At the time of this document preparation, the Innovation board has not been set up yet. This is planned do happen in year 1 of the project.

The SILLs cluster Leads will own the execution of the business development plans within each cluster.

The Innovation Management Board reports to the Council of Partner’s composition is shown in the diagram below.

Figure 4 Innovation Management Board composition – Clusters, organisations, relevant SILLs

All Partners

The general requirements for all ZeroW Consortium partners are set in the CA, section 4: Responsibilities of Parties. According to clause 4.1, each partner:

- undertakes to **take part in the efficient implementation of the Project, and to cooperate, perform and fulfil, promptly and on time, all of its obligations under the GA and CA** as may be reasonably required from it and in a manner of good faith as prescribed by Belgian law.
- undertakes to **notify promptly**, in accordance with the governance structure of the Project, any significant information, fact, problem or delay likely to affect the Project.
- shall promptly **provide all information** reasonably required by a Consortium Body or by the Coordinator to carry out its tasks.
- shall take **reasonable measures to ensure the accuracy** of any information or materials it supplies to the other Parties.

3. Project Management Plan

In this section

The main objective of this section is to provide clarity of scope, roles, timelines and to foster collaboration through highlighting early in the project the input/output task dependencies and stimulate the information exchange between the respective delivery parties.

The content below is based on the GA Annex 2 Part A and is expanded with the planning work done in the first month of the project, including the Pre-kick-off Technical Workshop held on the 5th of January 2022 with the WP and Task Leads to clarify the roles and responsibilities and identify work dependencies between the WPs and Tasks. Therefore, the plan must be used in conjunction with the agreement, where the scope of work is detailed for WPs and level 1 tasks.

ZeroW project delivery organisation information is summarised per WP, including the high-level work breakdown, timelines, roles and responsibilities, resources to be committed, deliverables to be produced.

The plan presented below represents the ZeroW baseline, against which the project progress will be monitored (see section

Project delivery plan

The delivery of ZeroW scope is organised in 11 work packages to be delivered in a 48-month period. The project Gantt chart, containing level 1 Tasks, deliverables and milestones is included in Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

The WP-specific information is structured in the following way:

WP[X]

- *Objectives, flow of work, interoperability*
Depicts the level 1 tasks flow chart and their contribution to the verification instruments and respectively – project objectives realisation. Provides information on the expected information inflows from and outflows to other parts of the project.
- *Roles and responsibilities, staff effort*
Lists the roles and responsibilities for the respective partners involved in the tasks, using the [RACI matrix](#) terminology (see the textbox to the right). The effort for each participant as budgeted in the GA is also provided.
- *Main outputs*
Includes information for the deliverables in table format, also incorporating the internal versions of the respective deliverables, where such are planned.

WP1 Modelling FLW economics from F2F

The WP1 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M38. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP1 will outline a conceptual framework for measuring the economic effects of FWL along the food chain. It will develop an economic model encompassing the food supply chain actors and validate it by the SILLs. Policy simulations will be run to quantitatively assess various FLW interventions.

The economic model and the empirical results obtained will contribute towards the achievement of ZeroW objective O7, including through close collaboration with WP8.

Explained

RACI MATRIX

R – Responsible

The Partner that actually complete the task, i.e. is responsible for action/implementation. The responsibility for the task can be shared between multiple partners. The work to be done by the Responsible Partners is determined by the “A” (Accountable) Partner.

A – Accountable

This is the Partner that is ultimately answerable for the activity or decision. This includes responsibility for decision making related to activity execution. There must be only 1 accountable organisation per action.

C – Consulted

The role of the “Consulted” is typically reserved for subject matter experts that are consulted prior to decision or action. “C” also could be Partners, accountable for other tasks that are in some form of dependency with the respective task. For example, the “A” for a predecessor task can be consulted with regards to expected completion date, format of results that are input for the current task, etc.

I – Informed

These are the Partners that need to be informed after a decision/action is taken.

Figure 5 WP1: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP1 will interact with tasks in WP2 (Data Space), WP4 (SI Management and Demonstration), WP7 (Exploitation and Commercialisation) and as stated above – with WP8. The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 5 WP1 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
T4.3	SILLs leaders	Details on the planned (reuse and reduce) interventions	T1.1, Frans, TiU
		What kind of policies to be modelled? E.g., donations	T1.2, Dusan, WU
		Empirical data to be run in the model	T1.3, Dusan, WU
T5.1	Debolina, DIGI	Definitions	T1.1, Frans, TiU
WP8	Antoine, SAFE	What kind of policies to be modelled? Exact timing to be specified.	T1.2, Dusan, WU
		Who decides on the selection of sectors/commodities	T1.3, Dusan, WU
Outputs to			
WP7	T1.1, Frans	Model actors' names / definitions to be used in Market analysis for consistency in naming	T7.1, Kata, ICP
WP8	T1.3	Simulation results	T8.x, Antoine, SAFE

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP1 is led by Wageningen University, Dusan Drabik is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 5 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 6 WP1: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	WU	DIGI	ITA	ITC	TIU	
WP1	Modelling FLW economics from F2F	49.5	6	9	2	9	75.50
T1.1	FLW conceptual model	R 6.5	R 2	R 3	R 2	A 6	19.50
T1.2	FLW economic model development & SIC-based validation	A 26	R 2	R 3		R 2	33.00
T1.3	Modelling the impact of FLW operational & policy interventions at the meso (food sector) and macro (EU) levels	A 17	R 2	R 3		C 1	23.00

Definitions:

- R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
- A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)
- C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
- I – Inform (no cell colour)

In T1.1, TiU is leading the delivery and the production of the deliverable (D1.1 FLW conceptual model) with the active support and contribution from WU. DIGI, ITA and ITC review and comment on draft D1.1.

WU is leading the work in T1.2 and is the main contributor to D1.2 FLW economic model. The rest of the partners involved (DIGI, ITA, ITC and TiU) contribute by reviewing and commenting on the draft deliverable, including the incorporation of the inputs from WP5 and T1.1.

The roles and responsibilities in T1.3 are similar to the ones in T1.2. Here participation of a subcontractor for delivering the GE model is expected.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP1 are summarised in the table below.

Table 7 WP1: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Due Date
D1.1	FLW conceptual model	TIU	R	PU	FLW conceptual model – Will provide a conceptual model for the FLW economic effects.	6
D1.2	FLW economic model	WU	R	PU	FLW economic model – Will deliver a SILL-validated model.	24
D1.3	Empirical results	WU	R	PU	Empirical results – Will provide results of modelling FWL interventions.	38

WP2 OFLW Data Space

The WP2 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M46. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP2 will establish semantic interoperability through a managed European OFLW Data Space for the data sharing needed for reducing FLW, thus overcoming the fragmentation of data generated by the farming, supply chain, policy and research communities by stimulating the interoperability between data sources. The delivery team will also create a federating catalogue to ensure interoperability between data sources.

WP2 will set up an approach for defining the collaborative business and governance models for data sharing in OFLW and will support the SILLs in applying those to their specific areas of work.

Finally, the WP2 will develop an integrated kit to 'onboard' the SILLs and other OFLW initiatives, that can be used during and after the project.

WP2 will deliver ZeroW objective O2 as depicted on Figure 6 below.

Figure 6 WP2: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP2 will interact with tasks in WP1 (Modelling), WP3 (Smart Applications), WP4 (SI Management and Demonstration), WP7 (Exploitation and Commercialisation) and WP9 (Cooperation with EC). The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 8 WP2 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
WP1	WU	Description of strategic models	All inputs to be coordinated by Frank, TNO
WP3	WIT	Requirements for Smart Applications including actors & recipes	
T7.5	F6S	WP7 on exploitation and business models – commercial stakeholder groups	
T7.3	ICP	Methodology to support, Description of identified collaborative business models , also T7.2	
WP4	BIOS	Information requirements: business use cases, actors, value networks, business models, governance and information models to determine which data is used when, where and by whom.	
T4.1	ILVO	Part of D4.1 is definitions – we are interested in the organizations and networks behind standards and definitions	
		Enhancing actors capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations (+6.3) as users of D2.7	
T4.3	SILL6, Roberto, ASINCAR	Integrate, interact with data/outputs of SILL6	
	SILL1, Matina, UM	Contribute to establishing data models and pipelines for managing (storing/processing. /..) data.	
T5.1	Debolina, DIGI	Related initiatives https://euhubs4data.eu/services/ Other catalogues, e.g. IoF2020, IoT catalogue – organizations and network behind the FLW data standards BDVA, IDSA, https://www.ai4europe.eu/	
T6.2	ILVO	Task on scaling and systemic innovation	
Outputs to			
WP1	All outputs to be coordinated by Frank, TNO	Data Space specifications for FLW modelling purposes	T1.2, Dusan, WU
WP3		Data Space specifications for FLW ‘analytical components’ purposes	Paul, WIT
		Collaborative Business Models and governance models for FLW ‘analytical components’ purposes	
WP4		Help develop the data driven solution for SILL1, building a modern big data model, establishing data pipelines,	SILL1, Jure (UM)
		Data Space specifications for FLW applications in SILLs	T4.2, BIOS
		Collaborative Business Models and governance models for applications in SILLs	
		WP2 input to WP4 Strategic Plan (T4.2 – D4.3-M3) Link with another “pilot” SILL	
		Description of identified business services and requirements for governance procedures	

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
		SILLS to become ambassadors and “happy customers”	T4.3 BIOS
T7.1		Support with dataspace market analysis.	T7.1, Maria Jose (ICP)
T7.4		Input information for dataspace business models	T7.4, Kata (ICP)
WP9		Outreach to FLW projects to use the OFLW Data Space	Angele, ICLEI

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP2 is led by TNO, Frank Berkers is the assigned WP Lead. TNO are supported by 10 other partners in the delivery of the work. Their roles and responsibilities are shown in the RACI matrix for the WP (see Table 9 below).

Table 9 WP2: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	WIT	BIOS	DIGI	ILVO	KNT	ITC	ATTI	ICCS	ASINCAR	
WP2	FLW digitalisation service portfolio & infrastructure	5.5	36.5	11.5	10	4	12	20	4	3	7	1	114.50
T2.1	Design and definition of the OFLW Data Space		A 9	R 6	R 3	C 1	R 7	R 3	R 2		R 4		35.00
T2.2	Governance and collaborative business model approach for OFLW applications and OFLW data space	C 1.5	A 8	R 5.5	R 2	C 1	C 1	R 5		C 1			25.00
T2.3	Establishing the OFLW Federated Catalogue and Data Space	C 1	A 9.5		R 2	C 1	R 3	R 5		C 1	R 3		25.50
T2.4	Establishing OFLW data space and governance and business models in the ZEROW SILLS	R 3	A 10		R 3	C 1	C 1	R 7	R 2	C 1		C 1	29.00

Definitions:

- R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
- A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)
- C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
- I – Inform (no cell colour)

The TNO team is leading all the tasks in WP2 and are the major contributor in all the deliverables. They are actively supported by KNT, ILVO, WIT, ITC and ICCS. BIOS are providing the live link with the work in WP4. KNT will help design the data space, identify and integrate data sources and identify business models that help towards Zero FLW. ITC will assess relevant data sources for all actors in the food supply chain, build the dataspace hardware infrastructure and develop data governance model. WIT will ensure that the stakeholders do benefit from the data driven strategies. ICP will stay in touch with the work in WP2 with regards to the possible commercialisation opportunities and the business models developed as well as in relation to the dataspace market analysis. The rest of the partners have a consulting role with regards to specific implementations of the dataspace and the respective governance models.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP2 are summarised in the table below.

Table 10 WP2: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	Due Date
						V1	V2	
D2.1	SotA, requirements, initiatives	TNO	R	PU	SotA, requirements, initiatives.			8
D2.2	Reference document with specification of connectors	TNO	R	PU	Reference document with specification of connectors, R, PU, Internal version 1 M12, Final version M24	12		24
D2.3	Archetypes and methodology for designing Governance and Collaborative Business Models for OFLW Data Space and Applications	TNO	R	PU	Archetypes and methodology for designing Governance & Collaborative Business Models for OFLW Data Space and Applications.			12
D2.4	Widely endorsed whitepaper/charter defining the federated catalogue & governance procedures	TNO	R	PU	Widely endorsed charter defining the federated catalogue and governance procedures, R, PU, Internal version 1 M24, Final version M46	24		46
D2.5	OFLW Dataspace	TNO	OTHER	PU	OFLW Dataspace, OTH, PU, Internal version 1 M14, Internal version 2 M28, Final version M42.	14	28	42
D2.6	Methodology and learnings from applying the prototype kit to the SILLs	TNO	R	PU	Methodology and learnings from applying the prototype kit to the SILLs, R, PU, Internal version 1 M18, Final version M42	18		42
D2.7	Guidelines for establishing interoperability, collaborative business models, governance for (non-ZeroW) OFLW initiatives	TNO	R	PU	Guidelines for establishing interoperability, collaborative business models, governance for (non-ZeroW) OFLW initiatives, R, PU, Internal version 1 M30, Final version M46.	30		46

WP3 ZERO Systemic Innovation Support Tools to assist developers design and implement SIC support applications

The WP3 starts at M3 and is planned to complete at M46. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP3 will provide a suite of Data-driven Intelligence Services consisting of 4 key components:

- Big Data Infrastructural Services, delivered through T3.1, led by KNT.
- 0FLW Application Enhancement and Integration Services in support of the SILLs solutions, delivered through T3.4, led by WIT.
- AI Analytics and Visualization Services supporting key aspects of FLW management, delivered through T3.3, led by ITA.
- SILL Actors Incentives Assessment and Optimisation Services, delivered through T3.2, led by ITA.

Figure 7 WP3: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP3 will interact with tasks in WP2 (Data Space), WP4 (SI Management and Demonstration), WP5 (SI Assessment) and WP7 (Exploitation and Commercialisation). The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 11 WP3 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
WP1	Dusan, WU	Align with WP1 modelling and interactions., for conceptual models and economic model – need to know relationships between parameters for each use case.	T3.1, Antonis, KNT
WP2 T2.3	Frank, TNO	Services identified, metadata	T3.1, Antonis, KNT
		Requirements Analysis about data types, sizes, data structures Collaboration for requirements analysis	T3.3, David, ITA T3.4, Paul, WIT
WP4	Tanja, BIOS	Data collection from SILLs and expert opinions, to set parameters for modelling, actors, expected behaviour.	T3.1, Antonis, KNT T3.4, Paul, WIT
		Actors, workshop discussion with experts from SILLs to identify relations and know what model is suitable	T3.3, David, ITA
		Requirements analysis	T3.3, David, ITA T3.4, Paul, WIT
Outputs to			
WP7	Paul, WIT	Identified results for commercial exploitation within WP3 and inputs regarding those to all WP7 tasks	Kata, ICP Lina, F67
WP5	Paul, WIT	Assessment of SILL Impacts, Interpretation of Results	Debolina Paul, DIGI
WP4	T3.1, David, ITA	Technology Pool	Fleur, EV-ILVO
WP2	Frank, TNO	Data Space specifications for FLW 'analytical components' purposes	T3.1, Paul, WIT
		Collaborative Business Models and governance models for FLW 'analytical components' purposes	

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP3 is led by Waterford Institute of Technology, Paul Malone is the assigned WP Lead. WIT is supported by 10 other partners in the delivery of the work. Their roles and responsibilities are shown in the RACI matrix for the WP (see Table 12 below).

Table 12 WP3: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	WIT	DIGI	VLTN	ITA	KNT	ITENE	AFL	ICCS	ASINCAR	
WP3	ZEROW Systemic Innovation Support Tools to assist developers design and implement SIC support applications	12.0	4.0	22.0	10.0	13.0	27.0	11.0	4.0	8.0	25.0	2.0	138.00
T3.1	Big Data Infrastructural Services	R 3.0	R 2.0	R 5.0			R 4.0	A 5.0		R 2.0	R 12.0		33.00
T3.2	SILL Actors Incentives Assessment and Optimisation	R 3.0		R 6.0		R 4.0	13.0				R 3.0	C 2.0	31.00
T3.3	AI Analytics and Visualization Services	R 3.0	C 1.0	R 5.0	R 5.0	R 4.0	10.0	R 6.0			R 3.0		37.00
T3.4	OFLW Application Enhancement and Integration Services	R 3.0	C 1.0	A 6.0	R 5.0	R 5.0			R 4.0	R 6.0	R 7.0		37.00

Definitions:

- R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
- A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)
- C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
- I – Inform (no cell colour)

T3.1 is led by KNT, who will facilitate algorithms that will be developed in T3.3, complement data space offering, orchestrated queries across data space, Kafka, Apache, SPARK. KNT will be supported by WIT who will contribute to developing generic analytics algorithms, ITA with regards to the data schema and the potential embedding of a Data lake, and ICCS with facilitating Recipes. TNO and ICP participation is linked with the provisioning of the input/output information from WP2 and WP7 respectively. AFL will also assist in the task.

T3.2 is led by ITA, who will create models to represent impact of different companies about incentives to reduce food waste; Realign with WP1, high level models about food waste in general; Focus on company levels, talk to SILLs about important parameters to reduce waste; Create models to optimize supply chain; Look at medium- and long-term impact; Simulate a digital twin of end-to-end supply chain; Identify best SILL for those activities. ITA will be supported by WIT by developing models, predictive data analytics and by VLTN who will provide Agent-based modelling and system dynamics models. ICP will assist with model development and exploitation, and ICCS will model and service development. ASINCAR will assist in the integration of WP3 tools in SILL 6.

T3.3 is led by ITA again. Here ITA will develop a common framework of intelligent algorithms for different SILLs, suggest new algorithms for existing analytics and assist in evaluating data and what SILLs can do with it. ITA will also test models with reinforcement learning for supply chain optimisation. KNT will support the task delivery through image processing, NLP and together with WIT - Support AI analytics development and visualisation. TNO will assist with interfacing with WP2. DIGI, VLTN, ICP, and ICCS will assist with model and service development.

T3.4 is led by WIT, who will perform the requirements analysis, design and develop smart applications, and integrate & test the smart app in the SILLs. WIT will also coordinate the information exchange with WP2 (TNO) and will collaborate with WP2 (TNO) on SDK libraries development. ICCS, AFL, DIGI, VLTN, ITENE, ICP will all work towards services design and development.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP3 are summarised in the table below.

Table 13 WP3: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	Due Date
						V1	V2	
D3.1	Big Data Infrastructural Services	KNT	OTHER	PU	Big Data Infrastructural Services, OTH, PU, Internal version 1 M9, Final version M20	9		20
D3.2	SILL Actors Incentives Assessment and Optimisation	ITA	OTHER	PU	SILL Actors Incentives Assessment and Optimisation, OTH, PU, Internal version 1 M14, Internal version 2 M28, Final version M46.	14	28	46
D3.3	AI Analytics and Visualization Services	ITA	OTHER	PU	AI Analytics and Visualization Services, OTH, PU, Internal version 1 M14, Final version M28.	14		28
D3.4	Application Development Services, Technologies, Connectors and Tools	WIT	OTHER	PU	Application Development Services, Technologies, Connectors and Tools, OTH, PU, Internal version 1 M14, Final version M28.	14		28

WP4 Systemic Innovation demonstration

The WP4 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M48. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP4 scope is focused on the demonstration of the systemic innovations, the management of the SILLs communities and their work. It will facilitate the SILLs work through the provisioning of an enabling Living Lab environment, implementation of learning feedback cycles and ensuring strong interactions with the rest of the project activities. WP4 will support the evolutionary process of the SILLs from a baseline to a higher level of systemic innovation readiness.

Figure 8 WP4: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP4 will interact with all of the rest of the project’s work packages. The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 14 WP4 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
WP2	Frank, TNO	Technology pool.	T4.1, Bart, ILVO
WP3	Paul, WIT	Technology pool. WP3 contribution to T4.1 in M9, 12,18	T4.1, Bart, ILVO
WP8	Antoine, SAFE	Contributing to the FLW definition	T4.1, Bart, ILVO
WP3, WP5-8	WP Leads	Systematic innovation management and evolution of the SILLs	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS
All WP	WP Leads	Inputs to SILL strategic plan template, and SILL progress report template	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS
Outputs to			
T1.1	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS	Details on the planned (reuse and reduce) interventions	T1.1, Frans, TiU
T1.2	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS	What kind of policies to be modelled? E.g., donations	T1.2, Dusan, WU
T1.3	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS	Empirical data to be run in the model	T1.3, Dusan, WU
All WPs	T4.2, Tanja, BIOS	SILL strategic plans and progress reports	All WP Leads

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
WP5	T4.1, Bart, ILVO	Development of Systemic Innovation Readiness Level to be used by all SILLs	T5.1, Debolina, DIGI
		TBC	T5.2, Daniel, ITC

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP4 is the largest WP not only in terms of budget, but in terms of participating organisations. A total of 38 partners are delivering work, related to Systemic Innovation Demonstrations. The WP4 is led by Biosense (BIOS), Jovana Vlaskalin is the assigned WP Lead.

T4.1 is led by ILVO, who will be coordinating the work to equip the SILLs with resources to support their activities of ideation, prototyping, testing, demonstrating, commercialising and scaling up. ILVO will be supported by WIT, BIOS, SAFE, ITC, ATIT, TiU. The addressing of maturity gaps required for the successful implementation of the SILLs will be assisted by SAFE and T4.2 participants VLTN, TiU and WU.

T4.2 is led by BIOS who are responsible for the SILLs communities' management and coordination, including the development of formal strategic plans for the SILLs. For those activities BIOS will be supported by ICP, WIT, DIGI, VLTN, TNO, F6S and representatives from all SILLs.

BIOS is also leading T4.3 where their main role is to coordinate the work in the SILLs for the establishment and implementation of their innovation processes from ideation to demonstration for achieving higher impact and steering transition towards a near zero food systems. All the effort for the delivery of the systemic innovation demonstrations by the SILL partners is included in this task. F6S has a consultative role with regards to links with the Commercial ecosystem created in T7.5 and the validation of the SILLs results through it.

The partners' roles and responsibilities are shown in the RACI matrix for the WP (see Table 15).

Table 15 WP4: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	WU	TNO	WIT	BIOS	DIGI	ILVO	SAFE	VLTN	ITC	ITENE	ATIT	ATC	FCTA	IFAPA	AFL	TiU	NVMMT	SONAE	GLC	MST	ART21	LVPA	SFC	F6S	ALL	UMINHO	ISP	OVAM	KGZS	UM	DIL	ASINCAR	ALDELIS	TERMO	EROSKI	VBL	SVZ			
WP4	Systemic Innovation demonstration	2	70	2	3.5	20.0	2	45	2	2	36	61.5	27	16	12.5	4	35	70	18	26	17.5	21.5	23	3	8	2	35	19.5	10.7	5	29	36	11	47	28.5	23.5	17.5	4	5	801.20		
T4.1	Shared resources for Systemic Innovation				R	R	A	R		R			R					R																								24.00
T4.2	Management of the SILL communities / the shared resources	R	R	R	R	A	R	R		R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R		R	R	R	R	R	R	C	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	66.50
T4.3	Systemic innovation management and evolution in the SILLs		R			1A	R				R	5R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	C	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	710.70	

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
I – Inform (no cell colour)

Due to the specific nature of the work in WP4, namely facilitating, managing and delivery of 9 individual SI demonstrators (Systemic Innovations Living Labs – SILLs), the roles and responsibilities are further broken down to reflect the participations of the partners in the individual SILLs.

Each SILL has a lead organisation, depicted in bold. Additionally, the SILLs have appointed SILL coordinator as the main contact person, contact point for business related activities and technical contact (specifically for cooperation with WP2 and WP3), Commercial contact (for collaboration with WP7) and also a contact point for Communication related tasks and activities related to cooperation with other services and initiatives (to liaison with WP10 and WP9). This division of roles within SILLs will allow smoother communication and cooperation between WPs and SILLs on a specific actions and tasks. This information has been captured in the Project Contact list, which is accessible to all ZeroW Consortium partners.

Figure 9 WP4: SILLs Partners and roles

Key:

- Participants in the main tasks, but not in the SILLs are indicated in dark green rectangles and white font.
- Participants in a specific SILL are grouped in a frame with the respective SILL number in the lower right corner. The colour coding is to visually distinguish the individual SILLs. The SILL lead is marked with bolded frame and font, and is at the first position in the SILL participants list.
- SILLs 7 and 9 share the same team members and for simplicity are represented in one frame. The lead of the respective SILL is indicated with a number after the name of the organisation.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP4 are summarised in the table below.

Table 16 WP4: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	DD
						V1	V2	
D4.1	Systemic Innovation maturity gaps	EV ILVO	R	PU	Systemic Innovation maturity gaps – Will address gaps required by the demonstrations.			6
D4.2	SILL tools	EV ILVO	R	PU	SILL tools – Will provide participation & systemic thinking tools.			6
D4.3	SILL Strategic Plans	BIOS	R	CO	SILL Strategic Plans – Will detail objectives & procedures.			3
D4.4	SILL Periodic Evaluation Reports	BIOS	R	CO	SILL Periodic Evaluation Reports, R, CO, Internal version 1 M14, Internal version 2 M36, Final version M46.	14	36	46
D4.5	Post-project SILL sustainability/funding strategies	BIOS	R	CO	Post-project SILL sustainability/funding strategies.			46
D4.6	Systemic Innovation solutions for reduced FLW and unsustainable packaging	BIOS	R	PU	Systemic Innovation solutions – Will present the evolution and results of the ZeroW innovations for reduced FLW & unsustainable packaging.			46
D4.7	Systemic Innovation Management – Lessons Learned & Best Practices	BIOS	R	PU	Systemic Innovation Management-Lessons Learnt – Will provide systemic innovation management best practices.			46

The outputs from the systemic innovation demonstrators are listed in Table 17 below. Additionally, all the SILLs will contribute towards the Food chain Systemic Innovation Readiness assessment.

Table 17 SILLs main outputs

SILL	Title	Output
1	FLW monitoring & assessment	Open, data-driven IT solution for FLW monitoring & assessment; FLW GHG impact assessment
2	Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products	IoT-Based food shelf-life calculation; Sustainable, functional and intelligent (deteriorating food alerting) packaging for fresh fish;
3	Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand	Optimal harvesting scheduling algorithms & services (to synchronise harvesting with downstream chain's capabilities/demand)
4	Mobile food valorisation as a service	Mobile processing unit as a service for optimising the use of edible biomass.
5	Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation	Ugly food identification platform (Multi-sensor & data service platform for classifying fruit products on aesthetics, quality & shelf-life)
6	Food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control & optimisation	FLW-optimized food processing advanced algorithms (production control and optimisation)
7	Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks	Food bank demand/supply prediction & FLW optimisation algorithms
8	Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications	Hermetic container for FLW pre-treated transportation; FLW logistics optimisation
9	'Fork to Farm to Fork' (3F): Informing and nudging consumers to make better choices through reverse	FLW-nutrient-GHG e-labels for meals, recipes & meal packages; Low FLW, high nutrient recipes based on ingredient availability; App for consumers

WP5 Systemic Innovation assessment

The WP5 starts at M3 and is planned to complete at M48. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP5 will develop and deliver a methodology for assessing FLW systemic innovations, which will be used (by WP5) to assess the SILL impacts, risks, sustainability trade-offs & level of 'just' allocation. Additionally, WP5 will provide interpretation of the results based on cluster, place, context actor and gender.

WP5 is working towards delivering the ZeroW objective O5 as shown in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10 WP5: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP5 will interact with tasks in WP1 (Modelling), WP4 (SI Management and Demonstration), WP7 (Exploitation and Commercialisation) and as stated above – with WP8. The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 18 WP5 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
T4.1	Bart, ILVO	Definition of systemic innovation readiness level	T5.1, Debolina, DIGI
WP4	Tanja, BIOS	Data collected during SILL executions will be necessary for T5.2. Data exchange done with T5.1 tool	T5.2, Debolina, DIGI
WP3	Paul, WIT	Assessment of SILL Impacts, Interpretation of Results	WP5, Debolina, DIGI
Outputs to			
T1.1	Debolina, DIGI	Definition of FLW conception model	Frans, TiU
WP2	T5.1, Debolina, DIGI	Related initiatives https://euhubs4data.eu/services/ Other catalogues, e.g. IoF2020, IoT catalogue – organizations and network behind the FLW data standards BDVA, IDSA, https://www.ai4europe.eu/	Frank, TNO
WP4	Debolina, DIGI	Systematic innovation management and evolution of the SILLs	Tanja, BIOS
		Inputs to SILL strategic plan template, and SILL progress report template	Tanja, BIOS
WP6	Debolina, DIGI	SI assessment results	Isabeau, ILVO

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP5 is led by Digiotech, Debolina Paul is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 13 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 19 WP5: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	DIGI	ILVO	VLTN	ITA	ITC	ITENE	ATIT	FCTA	SINTEF	NVMNT	ASINCAR	
WP5	Systemic Innovation assessment	2.0	2.0	30.0	1.5	3.0	3.0	20.0	8.0	6.0	1.0	0.5	2.5	1.9	81.35
T5.1	Development of an LCA and S-LCA based assessment methodology			A 6			C 1	R 2	C 1				C 0.5		10.50
T5.2	Assessment of SILL impacts, risks, sustainability trade-offs & level of 'just' allocation		C 1	1R 15	R 1.5		C 1	A 16.0	R 6	R 4	C 1		R 2	R 1.9	49.35
T5.3	Cluster-, place-, context- & actor-based consolidation & interpretation of results	R 2	C 1	A 9.0		R 3	C 1	R 2	C 1	R 2		C 0.5			21.50

Definitions:

- R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
- A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)
- C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
- I – Inform (no cell colour)

In T5.1, DIGI is responsible for the organisation of the work, and lead on methodology and tool developments. It will be supported by ITC, including with the Djust-connect platform development, which will be consulted with ITA, ITENE and NVMNT.

ITC are task lead for T5.2 and lead on the deliverable production organisation. Digi will support ITC with SILL specific assessments using T5.1 developed methodology. The rest of the involved partners (ITENE, ATIT, NVMNT, ASINCAR, ILVO, FCTA, TNO, ITA) will provide specific inputs needed for the assessment and validating the methodology.

DIGI is the task lead on assessment result validation (T5.3) and organisation of D5.3. ITC will support with the results interpretation. The rest of the partners will contribute to the validation of the cluster-, place-, context-, actor- & gender-based interpretation of results.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP5 are summarised in the table below.

Table 20 WP5: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	DD
						V1	V2	
D5.1	Impact assessment methodology	DIGI	R	PU	Impact assessment methodology.			8

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	DD
						V1	V2	
D5.2	SILL impacts assessment	ITC	R	PU	SILL impacts assessment – Will provide the results of assessing SILL impacts, risks, sustainability trade-offs & ‘just’ allocation, R, PU, Internal version 1 M24, Internal version 2 M30, Final version M46.	24	30	46
D5.3	Results interpretation	DIGI	R	PU	Results interpretations – Will provide cluster-, place-, context-, actor & gender-based interpretation of results, R, PU, Internal version 1 M26, Internal version 2 M32, Final version M48.	26	32	48

WP6 Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero FLW

The WP1 starts at M12 and is planned to complete at M46. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP6 will support the scaling up of the FLW systemic innovation solutions and approaches in EU regions with high potential. It will organise capacity building activities for food actors & consumers aiming for increased value (economic, environmental, social) from FLW innovations. Finally, it will build up regional specific upscaling strategies to stimulate investment in FLW reduction by private and public actors.

Figure 11 WP6: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies

Throughout its delivery, WP6 will interact with tasks in WP4 (SI Management and Demonstration), WP5 (SI Assessment), WP7 (Exploitation and Commercialisation),

WP8 (Policy recommendations) and with WP9 (Cooperation with EC initiatives and projects). The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 21 WP6 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
WP5	Debolina, DIGI	SI assessment results	Isabeau, ILVO
T7.1	Kata, ICP	Input from the market analyses with regards to the clusters.	T6.1 and T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO
T8.1	Antoine, SAFE	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways to contribute to the enhancing of the capacity	T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO
WP4	Tanja, BIOS	SILL strategic plans and progress reports	
Outputs to			
WP4	Isabeau, ILVO	Systematic innovation management and evolution of the SILLs	Tanja, BIOS
		Inputs to SILL strategic plan template, and SILL progress report template	Tanja, BIOS
WP5	T6.1, Isabeau, ILVO	Critical success factors identification – to feed in the assessment methodology	T5.1 Debolina, DIGI
WP7	T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO	Identification of measures to enhance actors' & consumers' capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations to feed into Customer validation in T7.2	T7.2 Kata, ICP
	T6.3, Lina, F6S	Identify whether there are any actions proposed in 6.3 that will impact the operational and financial model for the specific situations.	T7.3, Kata, ICP
WP9	Lina, F6S	Contribution to stakeholder mapping in relation to regional scaling initiatives.	Angele, ICLEI

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP6 is led by Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut, Isabeau Coopmans is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 8 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 22 WP6: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	BIOS	ILVO	VLIN	FCTA	F6S	ICLEI	
WP6	Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero FLW	6	4	10	34	17	4	14	7	96.00
T6.1	Critical success factors and incentives of actors in regions with potential to engage in FLW innovation	R 2	R 2	R 3	A 15	R 6	C 1		R 2	31.00
T6.2	Enhancing actors' & consumers' capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations	R 2		R 2	A 15	R 6	C 1			26.00
T6.3	Build-up regional scaling strategies to stimulate investment in FLW reduction by private and public actors	R 2	R 2	R 5	R 4	R 5	R 2	A 14	R 5	39.00

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)

A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)

I – Inform (no cell colour)

T6.1 and 6.2 are led by ILVO with the active support of VLTN. ICP, TNO, BIOS and ICLEI are contributing to the identification of the critical success factors and actors' incentives. ICP and BIOS are also supporting ILVO and VLTN with the actors' and consumers' capacity enhancement through the links with the Customer validation and solution alignment work and the inputs from the SILLS. FCTA provides information on ad-hoc basis for those two tasks.

T6.3 is led by F6S, who will be supported in the building of the regional strategies by the inputs from the SILLs (BIOS), ILVO, VLTN and ICLEI (in particular with liaison with other EC regional initiatives). ICP, TNO and FCTA will also collaborate to the strategies development.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP6 are summarised in the table below.

Table 23 WP6: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Due Date
						V1	
D6.1	Scale-up success factors and targeted EU regions	ILVO	R	PU	Scale-up success factors and targeted EU regions – Will define critical success factors for innovation scale-up and identify high-potential EU regions, R, PU, Internal version 1 M18, Final version M28.	18	28
D6.2	FLW capacity building	ILVO	R	PU	FLW capacity building – Will present activities, material & tools for appropriation value from FLW innovations, R, PU, Internal version 1 M36, Final version M46.	36	46
D6.3	Regional Scaling strategies	F6S	R	PU	Regional Scaling strategies – Will present strategies & activities to overcome scaling bottlenecks, R, PU, Internal version 1 M36, Final version M46.	36	46

WP7 Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs
 The WP7 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M46. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP7 will advance ZeroW's innovative solutions commercially and protect the commercially sensitive and strategic IP through 3 formal Patent filings. For the commercially exploitable project results, the WP7 will formulate a business- and market-relevant exploitation strategy with the end goal of self-sustaining revenues and a sustainable commercial trajectory. It will also anchor the exploitation, business models, licencing models and go-to-market strategy through robust market sector analyses and commercial solution alignment imperatives.

Figure 12 WP7: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP7 will interact with tasks in all ZeroW WPs. The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 24 WP7 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
T1.1	Frans, TiU	Model actors' names / definitions to be used in Market analysis for consistency in naming	T7.1, Kata, ICP
WP2	Frank, TNO	Support with dataspace market analysis.	T7.1, Maria Jose, ICP

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
T2.4		Support the exploitation of OFLW applications by developing appropriate governance & collaborative business models through the methodology developed in T2.2&T2.4.	T7.3, Kata, ICP
T3.2	ITA	Identify whether there are any incentives proposed in 3.2 that will impact the operational and financial model for the specific situations.	T7.3, Kata, ICP
	Paul, WIT	Identified results for commercial exploitation within WP3 and inputs regarding those to all WP7 tasks	Kata, ICP Lina, F6S
T4.2	Stavros, BIOS	List of commercial leads for each SILL	T7.2, Kata, ICP
		Links and on-boarding with the individual SILLS	
		Project results register periodic update by the SILLS, including indication of solutions Partners would like to exploit commercially	
		Identify stakeholders for clustering;	T7.5, Lina, F6S
		Identify events to present the partners/project/solutions and expand network	
T4.3	Stavros, BIOS	Which are the most immediate results/solutions/applications to materialise through the SILLS	T7.3, Kata, ICP
		Continuous interface between the SILLS business leads and the creation of the business models/plans	
T5.2	ITC	Validation of market needs analysis through assessment of SILLs	T7.2, Kata, ICP
		Feedback Loop with T5.3 up to M24 (starting of 5.3); afterwards an assessment of clustering done by F6S	T7.5, Lina, F6S
T5.3	Debolina, DIGI	Help to identify the actors for events, to create strategies and synergies	
T6.2	Isabeau, ILVO	Identification of measures to enhance actors' & consumers' capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations to feed into Customer validation in T7.2	T7.2, Kata, ICP
T6.3	Lina, F6S	Identify whether there are any actions proposed in 6.3 that will impact the operational and financial model for the specific situations.	T7.3, Kata, ICP
T8.3	Antoine, SAFE	Feedback loop, collective effort to known events, activities, policies > expand network	T7.5, Lina, F6S
T9.2	Angele, ICLEI	Information exchange/previous reports - if there is a work done by EC in the space of FLW market. Not necessarily market analysis from sister projects, but other commissioned work under EC guidance.	T7.1, Kata, ICP
WP10	Louise, FBCD	Attract attention of investors, community, share the work	T7.5, Lina, F6S
Outputs to			

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
WP4	Kata, ICP	Systematic innovation management and evolution of the SILLs	Stavros, BIOS
		Inputs to SILL strategic plan template, and SILL progress report template	
WP9	Lina, F6S	An initial version of clustering. To understand the stakeholders' clusters/groups and its relevance for the market segmentation	Angele, ICLEI
WP2	T7.5, Lina, F6S	WP7 on exploitation and business models – commercial stakeholder groups	Frank, TNO
	T7.3, Kata, ICP	Methodology to support, Description of identified collaborative business models , also T7.2	
WP6	T7.5, Lina, F6S	Input from the market analyses with regards to the clusters.	T6.1 and T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO
WP6	T7.3, Kata, ICP	Support of capacity building activities for NUTS2 regions by providing support through appropriate business models.	T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

The WP7 is led by Inlecom Commercial Pathways, Kata Trifkovic is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 18 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 25 WP7: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	WIT	BIOS	DIGI	ILVO	VLTN	ITA	KNT	ITC	ITENE	FCTA	IFAPA	AFL	NVMNT	F6S	ASINCAR	ALDELIS	
	Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs	36.0	7.0	1.0	9.0	6.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	6.0	1.5	16.0	2.0	1.0	110.50
T7.1	Market Sector Analyses	A 7	C 1		R 3				R 2	C 1	C 1	R 2	R 2		C 1					20.00
T7.2	Customer Validation & Solution Alignment	A 8		C 1	R 2					C 1	C 1	C 1			C 1					15.00
T7.3	Business Models and Business Plan	A 8	R 4		R 3	R 2	C 1				R 2	C 1	C 1		C 1			C 1		24.00
T7.4	IP Management and IP Protection	8.5			3			C 1	R 2	C 1		C 1				C 0.5		C 1	C 1	19.00
T7.5	Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation	R 4.5	R 2			R 2				C 1	C 1		C 1	C 1	R 3	C 1	A 16			32.50

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)

A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

I – Inform (no cell colour)

ICP is the task lead for tasks T7.1-7.4. F6S is the lead for T7.5.

In task 7.1 ICP will undertake a market analysis for specific segments, based on a common template and is responsible for the write up of the deliverable D7.1. TNO and BIOS will contribute to the market segmentation (review and input). BIOS, together with ITA, KNT, ITC, ITENE, FCTA and AFL will also provide input to the specific segments market analysis, following a common template provided by ICP.

In T7.2, ICP will provide the definitions of the use cases and organise the write-up of the deliverable. DIGI will support ICP in developing the approach for assessing solutions' alignment to client needs. WIT, KNT, ITC, ITENE and AFL will help in Use case definition (review and input on definition developed by ICP) and with the solution alignment assessment (in the respective area of expertise).

In T7.3, ICP will provide the Business Plans structure (including financial projections) and organise the deliverable write-up. TNO will provide assumptions and the resultant financial projections for the ZeroW platform (dataspace + intelligence services + apps). Additionally, TNO will participate in the feedback loop between tasks 7.3 and T2.2 and T2.4. TNO will also assist with the input from T6.3 on the proposed actions that will impact the operational and financial model for the specific situations. BIOS will provide the assumptions and the resultant financial projections for the ZeroW SILLs. BIOS will help identifying most immediate market opportunities, as well as provide support to consolidate use-cases into targeted cluster groups of applications, through periodic SILL reporting and lessons learnt. DIGI will provide intermediate results from the SILLs' demonstration and their interpretation to feed the business modelling exercise. ITC Will provide input from T5.2 on assessment of SILLs. ILVO, ITC, ITENE, FCTA, AFL and ASINCAR will also provide assumptions and the resultant financial projections for the ZeroW SILLs.

In T7.4 ICP will be responsible for the delivery of the IP management and protection of the project results and for the deliverable write-up organisation. ICP will be supported by BIOS, who will help with the organisation of the SILLs engagement and by VLTN, ITA, KNT, ITENE, NVMNT, ASINCAR and ALDELIS.

T7.5 is led by F6S who are responsible for the organisation of the Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem creation and of the deliverable write up. ICP will provide inputs from the Market analyses and Customer validation & solution alignment activities. F6S will be also supported by TNO, DIGI, KNT, ITC, FCTA, IFAPA, AFL and NVMNT.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP7 are summarised in the table below.

Table 26 WP7: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	DD
						V1	V2	
D7.1	Market Analyses	ICP	R	PU	Market Analyses - Will evidence market analyses around the FLW industry sector.			12

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	DD
						V1	V2	
D7.2	Customer Validation & Solution Alignment	ICP	R	PU	Customer Validation & Solution Alignment - Will distil the customer value proposition to achieve a predictable & sustainable licencing and commercial trajectory.			24
D7.3	Business Models & Business Plan	ICP	R	CO	Business Models & Business Plan - Will detail appropriate business models to acquire/retain customers and guide a commercialisation trajectory, R, CO, Internal version 1 M26, Internal version 2 M36, Final version M46.	26	36	46
D7.4	IP Management and Protection	ICP	R	CO	IP Management and Protection - Will evidence formal patent protection for 3 commercially strategic patents.			46
D7.5	Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem	F6S IE	R	PU	Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem Report - Will document and evidence a commercial eco-system cluster and deliver an incremental ecosystem progress growth report, R, PU, Internal version 1 M12, Internal version 2 M30, Final version M46.	12	30	46

WP8 Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW

The WP8 starts at M13 and is planned to complete at M46. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP8 will provide alternative transition pathways towards near-zero FLW and will define a 'just' transition pathway to near-zero FLW and intermediate targets. Finally, it will deliver short-, medium-term FLW reduction policy recommendations.

Figure 13 WP8: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP8 will interact with tasks in WP1 (FLW Modelling), WP4 (SI Demonstrations), WP5 (SI Assessment) WP6 (Capacity Building) and WP9 (Cooperation with EC initiatives). The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 27 WP8 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
T4.2	Tanja, BIOS	SILL strategic plans and progress reports	Antoine, SAFE
T1.3	Renzo, WU	Simulation results	
T5.2	ITC	Assessment of SILL impacts, risks, sustainability trade-offs & level of 'just' allocation	T8.2, Antoine, SAFE
T6.1	Isabeau, ILVO	Critical success factors and incentives of actors	T8.3, Antoine, SAFE
T6.2		Mechanisms for enhancing that can be applied on EU level	
T6.3	Lina, F6S	Regional strategies inputs	
Outputs to			
WP4	Antoine, SAFE	Systematic innovation management and evolution of the SILLs	Tanja, BIOS
		Inputs to SILL strategic plan template, and SILL progress report template	Tanja, BIOS
WP7	Antoine, SAFE	Feedback loop, collective effort to known events, activities, policies > expand network	T7.5, Lina, F6S
WP6	T8.1 Antoine, SAFE	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways to contribute to the enhancing of the capacity	T6.2, Isabeau, ILVO
WP1	Antoine, SAFE	What kind of policies to be modelled? Exact timing to be specified.	T1.2, Dusan, WU
		Who decides on the selection of sectors/commodities	T1.3, Dusan, WU

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

WP8 is led by SAFE Safe Food Advocacy Europe, Antoine D'haese is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 9 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 28 WP8: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	TNO	SAFE	VLTN	ITL	FCTA	IFAPA	SINTEF	ICLEI	ROBIN	
WP8	Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW	0.0	3.0	42.0	1.0	8.0	7.5	4.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	70.50
T8.1	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways		C 1	A 13		R 2	C 1	C 1				18.00
T8.2	A 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to near-zero FLW by 2050		R 2	A 15		R 3	R 3	R 2				25.00
T8.3	Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations			A 14	C 1	R 3	R 3.5	R 1.5	C 1	R 1.5	R 2	27.50

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)

A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

I – Inform (no cell colour)

Safe is the lead of all tasks within WP8, organise their execution and the deliverables write up and have the majority of the effort in each of the tasks. They are supported by TNO, VLTN, ITL, FCTA, IFAPA, SINTEF, ICLEI and ROBIN.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP8 are summarised in the table below.

Table 29 WP8: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Due Date
D8.1	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways	SAFE	R	PU	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways – Will report on the process and results of building pathways to near-zero.	24
D8.2	'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets	SAFE	R	PU	'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets to near-zero FLW by 2050 - Will report on the process and results of building a 'Just' transition pathway.	38
D8.3	Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations	SAFE	R	PU	Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations – Will define actor-, chain, gender- governance-specific recommendations.	46

WP9 Cooperation with EC services & other projects/initiatives

The WP9 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M48. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP9 will deliver an Action Plan for stakeholder & initiative engagement and cooperation with EC services and establish collaborative ecosystems with relevant stakeholders in different frameworks. Through this WP, ZeroW will engage with EU, National and global initiatives on a dialogue towards FLW policy, regulatory and commercialisation opportunities.

Figure 14 WP9: Links with objectives and verification instruments. Dependencies.

Throughout its delivery, WP9 will interact with tasks in WP1 (FLW Modelling), WP2 (Data Space), WP4 (SI Demonstrations), WP5 (SI Assessment) WP6 (Capacity Building), WP9 (Cooperation with EC initiatives) and WP10 (Dissemination). The relations with those work packages and the essence of the expected information exchange are presented in the table below.

Table 30 WP9 interoperability with the rest of the ZeroW project

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
Inputs from			
WP1	Frans, TiU / Renzo, WU	Contribution to stakeholder mapping – groups of stakeholders, included in the modelling, naming conventions	All inputs to be provided to Angele, ICLEI
WP2	Frank, TNO	Contribution to stakeholder mapping – understand the IT stakeholders Feedback loop with regards to similar Dataspace initiatives and projects	
WP4	Tanja, BIOS	Contribution to stakeholder mapping from the SILLs SILLs periodic reporting: results to be shared with initiatives/projects	

WP/ Task	Source task lead	Description of the required input	Input required by
WP6	Lina, F6S	Contribution to stakeholder mapping in relation to regional scaling initiatives.	
WP7	Kata, ICP	Contribution to stakeholder mapping based on the market analysis	
WP8	Antoine, Safe	Contribution to stakeholder mapping in relation to regulatory stakeholders	
WP10	Louise, FBCD	Contribution to stakeholder analysis - targeted messages	
		Assess whether the interest expressed by specific target groups/initiatives in D&C activities, deserves building a formal collaboration	
		D&C KPIs to refine WP9 Action plan	
All WP	WP Leads	Good practices and lessons learnt that can be shared externally with other initiatives/projects	
Outputs to			
All WP	Angele, ICLEI	Good practices and lessons learnt from other initiatives/projects that can be useful for ZeroW	WP Leads
WP10		Input from the stakeholder analysis to the dissemination strategy	Louise, FBCD
		Input from Action plan v1 to mapping the D&C activities: How to effectively reach out, engage, motivate and interact with external stakeholder and initiatives	

WP9 and WP10 are strongly interrelated, however, there is a different focus of the work in the two WPs. This complex relationship is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 15 Relationship between WP9 and WP19 scope and delivery

WP9, for the majority of its work, has more strategic focus. It represents the entire project, not individual partners/products. The WP9 delivery team looks at other projects and EC initiatives to find out common points of interests based on which we can build synergies. Once the synergies are identified, we see what kind of results from the SILLs we can bring on board, include it in the action plan and action it.

WP9 tries to find communalities and ways to work together. Through this identification it will feed WP10 with dissemination and communication opportunities. WP10 is responsible for D&C. In other words, WP9 is more like a preparation for WP10.

WP10 is to do with the dissemination and communication operative work. It provides direct link between the partners and the project products they are developing and the external community.

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

WP9 is led by ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH, Angele Tasse is the assigned WP Lead. There are a total of 13 partners participating in the delivery.

Table 31 WP9: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	BIOS	DIGI	SAFE	ITC	ITL	ITENE	FCTA	IFAPA	SINTEF	NVMNT	ICLEI	ROBIN	
WP9	Cooperation with EC services & other projects/initiatives	3.5	5.0	2.0	5.5	3.0	6.0	1.0	2.4	1.0	3.0	6.0	10.5	4.0	52.90
T9.1	Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement		C 1	R 2	R 1.5	C 1	R 3			C 1			A 6	R 2	17.50
T9.2	Cooperation with EC services & projects funded under the same topic	R 2	R 2		R 2	C 1	C 1		C 1.4				A 3	C 1	13.40
T9.3	Cooperation with other relevant European & global initiatives	R 1.5	R 2		R 2	C 1	R 2	C 1	C 1		A 3	R 6	R 1.5	C 1	22.00

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)
A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)
I – Inform (no cell colour)

ICLEI is the lead of T9.1 and will oversee and deliver Action Plan to effectively reach out, engage, motivate and interact with external stakeholder and initiatives. ITL, DIGI, ROBIN, and SAFE Will support with the mapping of stakeholders. ITL will lead the action plan section on logistics and transport (stakeholders, initiatives, platforms). DIGI will Action Plan section on digital (stakeholders, initiatives, platforms) and link with SILLs (in partnership with BIOS). ROBIN will lead on Action Plan section on social business & innovative food initiatives (stakeholders, initiatives, platforms). Safe will lead on Action Plan section on EU policymakers (stakeholders, initiatives, platforms). BIOS, ITC and IFAPA will be consulted with regards to the above. They will also be participating in meetings, responding to surveys, providing feedback to documents.

T9.2 is led by ICLEAI who will be reaching out to and engaging EC stakeholders (one-to-ones, EU Platform on FLW, etc.), LM focal point for collaboration network with other projects financed by the Green Deal Call under topic LC-GD-6-1-2020, engaging other projects. ICLEI will be supported by the Coordinator – ICP, focal point for collaboration network with other projects financed by the Green Deal Call under topic LC-GD-6-1-2020. BIOS Will provide the link with the SILLs for knowledge sharing with the external projects. SAFE Will suggest and participate in EC meetings to inform WP8. The resto of the involved partners Will support with projects and events participation, linking with respective Project teams and direct sharing of best practices and lessons learnt.

T9.3 is led by SINTEF.ng the cooperation with other relevant EU and global initiatives through links with the EAB, engagement with operating interactive innovation and international cooperation groups, such as FAO’s SAVE FOOD: Global Initiative on Food Loss and Waste Reduction, the Food Initiative of the Ellen Mc. Arthur Foundation, the Agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) Operational Groups, the Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) thematic groups. SINTEF Will organise the delivery and write up of the Liaison report that Will be kept up-to-date during the Project execution. In those activities SINTEF Will be supported by NVMNT, ICLEI, ITL, SAFE, BIOS and ICP. Furthermore, ITC, ITENE, FCTA, ROBIN Will consult the Task Lead.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP9 are summarised in the table below.

Table 32 WP9: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	Internal	Due Date
						V1	V2	
D9.1	Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement	ICLEI	R	CO	Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement – Will report on how external stakeholders & initiatives will be engaged and motivated to interact, R, CO, Internal version 1 M6, Internal version 2 M20, Final version M38.	6	20	38
D9.2	Liaison Report	ICLEI	R	CO	Liaison Report – Will report on liaison activities and their impact, R, CO, Internal version 1 M18, Internal version 2 M36, Final version M48.	18	36	48

WP10 Dissemination & communication

The WP10 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M48. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP10 are summarised in the table below.

Table 34 WP10: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Description	Internal	
						V1	DD
D10.1	Dissemination and Communication Master Plan	FBCD	R	CO	Dissemination & Communication Master Plan - Will outline planned communication & dissemination activities, R, CO, Internal version 1 M3, Final version M24.	3	24
D10.2	Dissemination and communication activities	FBCD	R	CO	Will report on dissemination & communication activities undertaken and their results.		48
D10.3	First set of Practice Abstracts	FBCD	R	PU	D10.3 will provide the Practice Abstracts. A total target number of 14 practice abstracts is foreseen for the project. Four of them are expected to be delivered in the first batch.		18
D10.4	Second set of Practice Abstracts	FBCD	R	PU	Project outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice. A total target number of 14 practice abstracts is foreseen for the project.		46

WP11 Project management

The WP11 starts at M1 and is planned to complete at M48. See Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart.

Objectives, flow of work, interoperability

WP11 will ensure the effective administration of the project activities according to the rules and regulations of the EU, and according to sound project management and coordination practices. It will ensure that all project outcomes are of high quality, meet their objectives and are delivered according to the agreed time- and resource-planning. WP11 will ensure that all potential risks are identified at an early stage, and appropriate mitigation actions are taken. Finally, the Coordinator will ensure through WP11 an effective interface with the EC.

Roles and responsibilities, staff effort

WP11 is led by the Project Coordinator, Inlecom Commercial Pathways, with Anna George as work package lead. All project partners participate in the delivery of WP11.

Table 35 WP11: RACI Matrix and efforts per task

Task #	WP/Task name	ICP	WU	TNO	WIT	BIOS	DIGI	SAFE	FBCD	VLTN	ITA	KNT	ITC	ITL	ITENE	AITT	ATC	FCTA	IFAPA	AFL	SINTEF	TIU	INVMMT	SONAE	GLC	MST	ARTZ1	LVPA	SFC	F6S	ALL	UMINHO	ICCS	ISP	OVAM	ICLEI	KGZS	UM	ROBIN	DIL	ASINCAR	ALDELIS	TERMO	EROSKI	VBL	SVZ		
WP11	Project management	23.5	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	.5	1	1	1	3.5	1	1	1	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	1	.5	.5	1	.5	2	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	.5	72.50	
T11.1	Administrative & financial management	A	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	50.50
T11.2	Technical coordination, quality control & risk management	A																																													14.50	
T11.3	Ethics requirements and data management policy																					A	3																							3.00		
T11.4	ZEROW overall impact assessment	R	4.5																																											4.50		

Definitions:

R – Responsible (green-coloured cells)

C – Consult (yellow-coloured cells)

A – Accountable (red-coloured cells)

I – Inform (no cell colour)

T11.1 is led by ICP who will organise the administrative and financial management of the project and respective reporting. The PC will also organise the work of the project governance bodies. All the partners participate in this task through meeting preparation, attendance and follow up and providing the required reporting at the intervals as required by the Coordinator.

T11.2 is also led by ICP, with the support of all WP leading organisations to ensure efficient technical coordination and quality control of the project results and improve the prospects for successful delivery by adequate risk management throughout the project delivery.

T11.3 is led and delivered by SINTEF who will produce the DMP and Ethics requirement deliverables and ensure the Partners adhere to those documents.

Finally, T11.4 is led by ICP and will produce the project overall impact assessment.

Main outputs

The main outputs of WP11 are summarised in the table below.

Table 36 WP11: Deliverables list

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination	Description	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Due Date
						V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	
D11.1	Project Handbook	ICP	R	PU	Project Handbook - Will present the main rules and approaches for inter-project coordination.							2

D No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dissemination	Description	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Internal	Due Date
						V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	
D11.2	Data Management Plan	SINTEF	OR DP	PU	Data Management Plan (DMP) - Will cover ethical and data management issues, R, PU, Internal version 1 M2, Internal version 2 M12, Internal version 3 M18, Internal version 4 M24, Internal version 5 M30, Internal version 6 M36, Final version M42. The DMP will identify the Open Research Data that will become available.	2	12	18	24	30	36	6
D11.3	Quality & Risk Assessment Reports	ICP	R	CO	Quality & Risk Assessment Reports - Will report on the quality of the project's results and any risks foreseen/addressed, R, CO, Internal version 1 M12, Internal version 2 M24, Final version M36.	12	24					36
D11.4	ZeroW's impact assessment	ICP	R	PU	ZeroW's impact assessment - Will present an overall assessment of the project impact.							48
D11.5	Proof of distribution of pre-financing	ICP	R	CO	This report will provide proof of the distribution of the grant pre-financing.							1
D12.1	H - Req. No. 1	SINTEF	ETHICS	CO	H - Requirement No. 1							3
D12.2	POPD - Req. No. 2	SINTEF	ETHICS	CO	POPD - Requirement No. 2							3
D12.3	NEC - Req. No. 3	SINTEF	ETHICS	CO	NEC - Requirement No. 3							3
D12.4	EPQ - Req. No. 4	SINTEF	ETHICS	CO	EPQ - Requirement No. 4							3

Monitoring and control of project work

The ZeroW Project Management Plan incorporates the project monitoring and control system ensuring the project scope will be delivered within the timelines of the project, the budget allocated to the Partners and with the expected quality so that the project objectives are achieved.

Milestones

The milestones set for ZeroW project provide a useful tool for monitoring of the project progress vs pre-identified important moments in the project, the ZeroW milestones.

Table 37 ZeroW Milestones

No.	Title	WP	Lead beneficiary	DD (Month)	Means of verification
MS1	Kick-off meeting	WP11	ICP	1	Kick-off Minutes
MS2	Website and communication materials available for use	WP10	FBCD	6	Website & communication material online
MS2	Commercial Eco System Cluster (50+relevant organisations) established	WP7	ICP	12	D7.5_v1 delivered
MS4	1st round of SILL demonstrations initiated	WP4	BIOS	14	D4.4_v1 delivered
MS5	FLW economic model validated by the SILLs	WP1	WU	24	D1.2 delivered
MS6	Customer Validation & Solution Alignment completed	WP7	ICP	24	D7.2 delivered
MS7	Application Development Services, Technologies, Connectors and Tools, available	WP3	WIT	28	D3.4_v2 delivered
MS8	Regional Scaling strategies established	WP6	ILVO	36	D6.3_v1 delivered
MS9	'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets validated	WP8	SAFE	38	D8.2 delivered
MS10	SILL demonstrations (3 cycles) completed	WP4	BIOS	46	D4.6 delivered
MS11	First release of Dataspace for the SILLs	WP2	TNO	14	D2.5_v1 delivered
MS12	First release of Intelligence Services for the SILLs	WP3	WIT	14	D3.3_v1 & D3.4_v1 delivered

Periodic progress monitoring

The periodic progress monitoring will be organised on the following levels:

WP level

The WP Leads will organise periodic WP operational meetings on which they will review the progress of the work done vs the plan, the plan for the following period, the deliverables status, risks and issues.

The WP periodic meetings dates will be included in the project calendar to provide transparency as well as opportunity for Partners to join. The meetings have to have as minimum attendees the representatives from the Partners who deliver work in

the current review period (between two WP progress meetings) and/or will deliver work in the next.

Project level

The regular project progress review is included in the agenda of the PSG meetings. On those meetings the WP leads present the progress achieved in the current reporting period, provide the plan for the following period and inform about the status of the deliverables. Any updates of the risk register are also discussed as well as collaboration between the work packages.

If there are any deviations from the plan, the WP lead flags this to the PC and provides a recovery plan which will steer the work back into the baseline plan framework. Should this be not possible, a change of the plan has to be evaluated by the PSG and then proposed for approval by the CoP as per CA requirements. Should the change of plan be approved by the CoP, this will trigger a GA amendment procedure.

Besides the project delivery monitoring and control through the PSG meetings, the ZeroW project plan implements another mechanism of monitoring and control, namely the internal project reporting from the WP Leads to the Coordinator.

The internal project reporting cycle will be quarterly and will follow the format/template of the project periodic reporting due at M18, M36 and M48. Besides providing a transparency for the achieved project progress to all the Consortium Partners, this periodic reporting has the function to facilitate and expedite the project periodic reporting for the commission, providing regular snapshot of the project at quarterly intervals with a granularity of the information that would not be possible to be achieved at the end of the reporting period when 18 months have passed.

The PC will provide the WP Leads with the template for the project reporting. The WP Leads will collect input from the delivery partners in the respective WP about their contribution in the current reporting period, will aggregate the information and will submit it to the PC.

The due date of each quarterly report is a month after the end of the quarter, e.g. for Q1 the internal periodic report is due on 30 Apr 2022.

Reporting to EC

At the end of each reporting period, the WP Leads will aggregate and summarise the information from the quarterly progress reporting and submit their contribution to the Project Coordinator in the template of the periodic progress report. The coordinator will review and finalise the report and submit it through the EC Portal.

Reporting of D&C activities

Partners should continuously report their dissemination and communication activities as they happen. When reporting the dissemination and communication activities to FBCD, WP10 Dissemination and Communication Lead, all the Partners should use the dedicated webform accessible via this link: <https://podio.com/webforms/27010388/2068492>

In this webform FBCD have defined most of the D&C targets in the project and the entries will allow the D&C lead to keep track of the progress against the ZeroW project KPIs.

The Partners can submit activities within 17 specific categories which are defined in ZeroW Grant Agreement and for which we have specific targets:

- Interviews/journalistic articles (All target groups including general public)
- Social media posts/web 2.0 tools (All target groups incl. general public)
- Graphic communication materials (leaflets, factsheets, roll ups, posters, videos)
- Journalistic articles written (All target groups incl. general public)
- Publication in newspapers and business journals (All target groups incl. general public)
- EC Dissemination routes (All target groups including general public)
- Presentations in conferences, seminars, trade shows, exhibitions. Face-to-face meetings (Industry)
- Articles and features in industry magazines (Industry)
- Promotion through professional organisations and networks (Industry)
- Scale up regional workshops (Industry)
- Direct contacts, personal invitations, conferences & other events (Policy actors & institutions)
- Submitted publications to peer-reviewed Journals (Scientific)
- Published publications in peer-reviewed Journals (Scientific)
- Lectures, webinars (Scientific)
- Participation in broad events (Scientific)
- Exhibitions & conferences (Scientific)
- Alternative D&C activities where the project was promoted (not incl. in GA targets)

For FBCD to maintain an overview of the progress we kindly ask you to submit any activities you do continuously. The procedure is simple and is explained in the 10 steps in the Guide, included in Annex II: Guide for reporting of D&C activities.

4. Quality Management Plan

In this section

Here you will find the description of the quality assurance process embedded in ZeroW project delivery to underpin the production of relevant and high-quality project outputs.

Quality Assurance Procedure

The WP leaders should ensure the timely delivery of the respective WP outputs that meet the quality expectations. They should review with the Lead Beneficiaries the status of each output/deliverable during the WP operational meetings and the WP Lead should report that during the PSG meeting WP review.

Figure 16 ZeroW Quality assurance process steps

The following procedure is applicable for all project deliverables. Please note that for the deliverables due to be submitted prior M6, the timings for the steps in the process will be individually defined together with the Lead beneficiary.

Deliverable structure ready

A month after the task where the respective deliverable originates, the Lead beneficiary produces a deliverable structure (table of contents), that is consistent with the requirements in the Grant Agreement, using the ZeroW Deliverable Template.

The Lead beneficiary can also complete the introductory document sections (mapping the deliverable vs. GA, introduction, etc.). An important part of the introductory Sections is the Deliverable own (quality) plan that describes the specific stages against which the deliverable will be reviewed to ensure the timely and quality output. Example of such plan is given in Table 38 below.

Table 38 Example of Deliverable quality and implementation plan

Gates	Gate Description	Date	Status
TOC	TOC and mapping the deliverable structure	31/01/2022 (M1)	Done
TOC Approved	WPL & Partners Approved (meeting to present TOC and discuss the approach; get comments from the partners and leave one week for the response)	28/02/2022 (M2)	In progress
25%	Background and Introduction (including methodology/ description of approach)	31/05/2022 (M5)	

Gates	Gate Description	Date	Status
	Research on what information is available/findable for each cluster; prepare the structure for each of the clusters based on the info available. If for specific cluster it is not possible to find info (MnM,...) contingency will be (i) describe the emerging market, (ii) speak to the relevant partners; (iii) speak with the EC to understand the needs (i.e. IT platform)		
50%	Written down the overview per wider sectors (Scenario 2) and how clusters fit there. Write-up on clusters sections started (where info in available). Contingency measures in progress for the clusters where info are missing. *Note: Write up of D7.1 can run in parallel with 7.2.1 Identify prominent customer personas & stakeholders (consumers/ exploiters). To be careful of wording, not to repeat same sections in 2 different deliverables.	31/07/2022 (M6)	
75%	Detailed market analysis per cluster completed (mapping ZeroW solutions, market drivers & dynamics, competitor analysis, barriers to entry, regulation).	30/09/2022 (M9)	
100%	Market summary and conclusions. Deliverable ready for peer review.	31/10/2022 (M10)	
DD	Deliverable deadline	31/12/2022 (M12)	

At this stage the Lead Beneficiary suggests a suitable Partner as a Quality reviewer and obtain their agreement to fulfil the role.

The Lead Beneficiary informs the PC about the name of the selected Quality Reviewer and the PC updates the ZeroW quality plan with this information.

ToC approved

The Lead beneficiary suggests what contributions/collaboration will be required by the respective delivery Partners in the WP and agrees that with them.

The Lead beneficiary reviews the structure of the deliverable, the deliverable plan and the agreed contributions by other Partners with the WP Lead and the Quality Reviewer.

This step has to be completed for a month after the deliverable structure has been developed, i.e., 2 months after the start of the Task in which the deliverable originates.

Deliverable implementation plan monitoring

The deliverable quality and implementation plan as created in step 1 is reviewed regularly during the WP operational meetings, with the Lead beneficiary reporting to the WP Lead the current status of the work vs what was planned. The dates for the identified “gates” in the plan are used to ensure the timely delivery of the work

and to facilitate the work planning, especially in the case of multiple partners involved and long period of delivery.

The Lead beneficiary should be in touch with the Quality Reviewer throughout the delivery production and consult if necessary. The Lead beneficiary should inform the Quality reviewer and the WP Lead if there are changes in the gate dates, so the Quality Reviewer can plan their time accordingly. The WP Lead informs the PC about any updates in the deliverables' quality and implementation plans.

In case that there is a risk of delay in delivery that will impact the deliverable due date, the Lead beneficiary informs the WP Lead and the PC as soon as possible, providing a motivation for the delay. This information will be shared with the Project Officer and included in the periodic reporting.

Deliverable ready for internal quality review

The deliverable content should be ready for internal quality review 3 months ahead of the deliverable due date. At that moment of time the Lead beneficiary submits it for review to the designated Quality Reviewer.

The Quality Reviewer checks the deliverable against the following quality criteria:

- **Relevance:** The output contributes to the project objectives achievement.
- **Compliance with GA requirements:** the output content reflects all the requirements for it described in Part A of the GA.
- **Good editorial quality:**
 - the deliverable structure is straightforward.
 - the language is suitable for the target auditoria.
 - there are no spelling and grammar mistakes.
 - when using information from other sources, correct citations are used and the EC requirements for referencing are followed.
 - the document looks good – the ZeroW templates are used, the images are of good quality.
 - The copyright for images from external sources is clearly stated in the image caption and permissions for using the images has been obtained.

The Quality Reviewer provides the Lead beneficiary with comments of how the quality of the document can be improved should there is a need for that.

Quality review complete

The Lead beneficiary addresses the comments from the Quality Reviewer and ensures the latter accepts the way they are addressed.

The Lead beneficiary submits the quality approved deliverable to the PC, ready to be uploaded in the EC portal in editable and in PDF format, one month prior the formal deliverable due date.

Deliverable ready for submission

The PC uploads the PDF version of the deliverable in the EC portal and notifies the Lead beneficiary and the WP lead for the successful upload.

The PC copies the two versions of the deliverable (editable and in PDF format) to the Final deliverables folder in the ZeroW Teams area General channel.

ZeroW Deliverable Quality Review Schedule

The ZeroW quality review schedule is integrated in the ZeroW Project plan in Excel. It reflects the steps of the quality review process described above and includes a time-phased visualisation of it.

At the time of this document submission, the deliverables quality reviews schedule is in draft form. The schedule will be completed in due course and will be kept updated throughout the delivery of the project.

Table 39 Preview of ZeroW deliverables quality review schedule

Task ID	Task Name	Beneficiary	TO	50	100	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48		
D1.1	T1.1	FLW conceptual model	TUJ																																																				
D1.2	T1.2	FLW economic model	WU			8	20	21	23	24																																													
D1.3	T1.3	Empirical results	WU			26	34	35	37	38																																													
D2.1	T2.1	SoA, requirements, initiatives	TNO			4	4	5	7	8																																													
D2.2	T2.1	Reference document with specification of connect	TNO	12		4	20	21	23	24																																													
D2.3	T2.2	Archetypes and methodology for designing Govern	TNO			2	8	9	11	12																																													
D2.4	T2.3	Widely endorsed whitepaper/charter defining the TNO	TNO	24		19	42	43	45	46																																													
D2.5	T2.4	OFLW Database	TNO	14, 28		13	38	39	41	42																																													
D2.6	T2.4	Methodology and learnings from applying the pro	TNO	18		13	38	39	41	42																																													
D2.7	T2.4	Guidelines for establishing interoperability, collabco	TNO	30		13	42	43	45	46																																													
D3.1	T3.1	Big Data Infrastructural Services	KNT	9		4	16	17	19	20																																													
D3.2	T3.2	SLL Actors Incentives Assessment and Optimis	ITA	14, 28		7	42	43	45	46																																													
D3.3	T3.3	AI Analytics and Visualization Services	ITA	14		7	24	25	27	28																																													
D3.4	T3.4	Application Development Services, Technologies, WIT	WIT	14		7	24	25	27	28																																													
D4.1	T4.1	Systemic Innovation maturity gaps	EV ILVO			2	2	3	5	6																																													
D4.2	T4.1	SLL tools	EV ILVO			2	2	3	5	6																																													
D4.3	T4.2	SLL Strategic Plans	BIOS			2	-1	0	2	3																																													
D4.4	T4.2	SLL Periodic Evaluation Reports	BIOS	14, 36		2	42	43	45	46																																													
D4.5	T4.2	Post-project SLL sustainability funding strategie	BIOS			2	42	43	45	46																																													
D4.6	T4.3	Systemic Innovation solutions for reduced FLW a	BIOS			7	42	43	45	46																																													
D4.7	T4.3	Systemic Innovation Management – Lessons Lea	BIOS			7	42	43	45	46																																													
D5.1	T5.1	Impact assessment methodology	DIGI			4	4	5	7	8																																													
D5.2	T5.2	SLL impacts assessment	ITC	24, 30		24	42	43	45	46																																													
D5.3	T5.3	Results interpretation	DIGI	26, 32		26	44	45	47	48																																													
D6.1	T6.1	Scale-up success factors and targeted EU region	EV ILVO	18		13	24	25	27	28																																													
D6.2	T6.2	FLW capacity building	EV ILVO	36		30	42	43	45	46																																													
D6.3	T6.3	Regional Scaling strategies	FES IE	36		30	42	43	45	46																																													
D7.1	T7.1	Market Analyses	ICP			2	8	9	11	12																																													
D7.2	T7.2	Customer Validation & Solution Alignment	ICP			14	20	21	23	24																																													
D7.3	T7.3	Business Models & Business Plan	ICP	26, 36		26	42	43	45	46																																													
D7.4	T7.4	IP Management and Protection	ICP			4	42	43	45	46																																													
D7.5	T7.5	Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem	FES IE	12, 30		4	42	43	45	46																																													
D8.1	T8.1	Alternative near-zero FLW pathways	SAFE			14	20	21	23	24																																													
D8.2	T8.2	'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets	SAFE			26	34	35	37	38																																													
D8.3	T8.3	Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendat	SAFE			36	42	43	45	46																																													
D9.1	T9.1	Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement	CLEI	6, 20		2	34	35	37	38																																													
D9.2	T9.3	Liaison Report	ICLEI	18, 36		2	44	45	47	48																																													

negative impacts on the work and maximising the opportunities which could make the work more efficient and effective.

The project will implement the methodology for Risk Management (RM) based on FERMA Standard, that represent the best practices for risk management developed for the Federation of the European Risk Management Associations by the Institute of Risk Management (IRM), the Association of Insurance and Risk Managers (AIRMIC) and the National Forum for Risk Management in the UK Public Sector (ALARM).

Risk management process

The risk management process described below will refer to the [FERMA RM Standard](#). A copy of the standard in English is uploaded in the Risk Management Folder in ZeroW Teams area, Channel WP11 – Project management. The definitions are quotations from the same document: FERMA: A Risk Management Standard, © AIRMIC, ALARM, IRM: 2002, translation copyright FERMA: 2003.

Figure 17 FERMA Risk Management Standard

Risk Assessment

The risk assessment includes the Risk analysis and the Risk evaluation.

Risk Analysis Steps

- **Risk Identification.** Identifying risks is a responsibility of each ZeroW Consortium Partner throughout the delivery of the project. Should a team member assume that an event might have an adverse effect on/or can

provide additional benefits to the project work or outcomes, he or she should report this as soon as practically possible to the respective WP lead.

Additionally, during the regular WP operative meetings, the WP leads will dedicate time to explore whether there are any new/uncaptured risks or opportunities.

- **Risk Description.** The objective of risk description is to display the identified risks in a structured format². The ZeroW PC have created a Risk Register to facilitate the structured RM process in the project, in which the risk descriptions are provided in the following format:

Table 40 Risk Register: structured description of risk

Field	Description
ID	A unique ID number for each risk for easy reference.
Raised by	The initials or name of the origin or the person that identified the risk.
Date reg.	The date that the risk was first recorded.
Category	The risk category selected from the list below ³ This enables the project risks to be analysed from a topic perspective.
Description (X,Y)	Description of the risk written as ' There is a risk that X) xxx because of Y) xxx '.
Consequence (Z)	Impact of the risk written as ' So that...Z '
Probability	The probability of the risk occurring, chosen from list with values Rare / Unlikely / Possible / Likely / Almost certain
Impact	The impact of the risk on the project, chosen from list with values Negligible / Low / Medium / High / Extreme
Score	The total score for the risk being a product of the probability and the impact with the maximum score being 25
Proximity	The proximity of the risk occurring. Select from the following: M1-6 / M7-12 / M13-18 / M19-24 / M25-30 / M31-36 / M37-42 / M43+
Status	Open or Closed. Note that Closed risks should be kept on the RR and not deleted.
Response type	The response to the risk using being one of the following Avoid / Reduce / Transfer / Share / Accept / Contingency.
Response description	The current approach to managing the risk which should be updated as the risk is reviewed.
Response Implemented?	Has the defined response been implemented? Yes or No.
Owner	The organisational acronym and the initials of the person in the project who is responsible for the risk.
Updated on	The date that the risk was last updated.

² FERMA: A Risk Management Standard, © AIRMIC, ALARM, IRM: 2002, translation copyright FERMA: 2003

³ Risk categories: Commercial, Quality, Technical, Strategic, Financial, Reputational, Political, Legal, Resources, Scheduling, Project Management, Adoption, Ethics.

Describing the risk in the Risk Register is a responsibility of the WP Lead, who should be supported by the partners, who have identified it in order to properly capture it and evaluate it afterwards.

The following risk categories have been set as part of the risk identification / description (in alphabetical order):

- Adoption
- Commercial
- Ethics
- Financial
- Legal
- Political
- Project Management
- Quality
- Reputational
- Resources
- Scheduling
- Strategic
- Technical
- **Risk Estimation.** This activity requires the WP Lead, together with the WP participating partners to estimate the scale of the event impact and likelihood (probability) of occurrence. The following scales are used:
 - Probability: Rare / Unlikely / Possible / Likely / Almost certain
 - Impact: Negligible / Low / Medium / High / Extreme

Risk Evaluation

The risk evaluation supports the decision making about the project risk significance and how it should be managed, by providing a prioritisation mechanism. The evaluation is done based on the risk analysis information captured in the Risk Register. The following decision-making matrix is applied in ZeroW project:

Table 41 Risk evaluation matrix

Impact	Extreme	5					
	High	4					
	Medium	3					
	Low	2					
	Negligible	1					
			1	2	3	4	5
			Rare	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
			Probability				

Each risk score is evaluated as a product of the impact and probability, using the scale in the matrix above. Thus, risks with score less than 4 are considered Low

(green), between 4 and 12 – Medium (amber), and above 12 – High (red). The maximum score is 25.

The Risk register file calculates the risks scores automatically and colours the score cell using the RAG colour codes based on the score.

Risk Reporting: ZeroW Risk register

The Risk reporting in ZeroW will be done in project internal level and externally – to the Commission through the EC Portal continuous reporting.

The internal project reporting will be done by the WP leads during the PSG meetings. The tool used to inform the internal and external reporting is the ZeroW Project Risk Register.

According to the FERMA Standard, (the Risk Register) “table can be used to facilitate the description and assessment of risks. The use of a well-designed structure is necessary to ensure a comprehensive risk identification, description and assessment process. By considering the consequence and probability of each of the risks set out in the table, it should be possible to prioritise the key risks that need to be analysed in more detail.”⁴

The ZeroW Risk Registered is set up as an Excel file with worksheets containing risk registers for each individual work package. This is done to accommodate the risk reviews performed during the on-going WP operational meetings, and to expedite the Risk reporting for the GSR, prepared by the WP leads.

The **ZeroW Project Risk Register** is located in ZeroW Teams area, channel WP11 – Project Management, folder Risk Management.

The PC will update the Critical Risks section if new risks, categorised as “High” (red), have been identified or their status has changed.

Risk Treatment

Risk treatment is the process of selecting and implementing measures to decrease the probability and/or impact of risks. In case of opportunities, the risk treatment identifies and implement measures to maximise the probability and/or the impact of the respective event.

For each identified risk, the WP lead should select the appropriate response strategy, e.g. to avoid / reduce / transfer / share / accept / provide contingency. And to describe it in the Risk register. The risk response appropriateness for already identified and described risks should be also reviewed during the WP progress

⁴ FERMA: A Risk Management Standard, © AIRMIC, ALARM, IRM: 2002, translation copyright FERMA: 2003

meetings and changes/updates – reported to PSG. This includes whether the risk response has already been implemented or no.

A person, responsible for the risk mitigation strategy implementation should be appointed as a Risk Owner and this should be documented in the Risk Register. The Risk Owner reports to the WP Leads any status changes in relation to the respective risk.

6. Communications Management Plan

In this section

Here you will find information about the management of the internal communication between the Partners during the delivery of the project to support a smooth and flowless collaboration between the large number of the ZeroW delivering organisations.

Contact list and maintenance

The project contact list is stored in the project teams area, channel General, tab **Contact List**. It provides the following information:

- Sheet **Project Partners**: Complete list of partners, involved staff members, roles within the project, contact details.
- Sheet **SILLs Overview**: SILL name, participating Partners, other members/stakeholders (not part of ZeroW Consortium), Main contact point for the SILL, Business contact, Technical contact, use cases included in the SILL.
- Sheet **SILLs Contact Info**: summary of SILLs contact (contact details easier to find than in the previous sheet).
- Sheet **Advisory Board**: details of advisory board members, including areas of interest, homepage, contact person and contact details. Tracking of Letters of invitation and NDAs also included.
- Sheet **Exploitation Stakeholders**: List of exploitation stakeholders that have provided letters of support, including their area of interest, contact person and contact details.
- Sheet **SILLs Exploitation Stakeholders**: Same as above, but stakeholders directly related to specific SILLs.
- Sheets with ZeroW project internal **mailing lists** (see section Mailing lists) for more information.

All the Partners have the obligation to maintain their contact details up to date. Should there is a change in the project team, the respective partner should either update the contact list or inform the Project Coordinator about the change.

Note: The contact list contains **personal information**: Names, business email addresses (and telephone numbers) of individuals. Please use the Contact list in compliance with the **GDPR** requirements. Do not provide access to this document to staff that is not involved in ZeroW delivery and does not need to have access to it. Do not include contact details of individuals who have not provided you with a written statement that they would like to be involved in communication regarding ZeroW delivery. Please, refer to the DMP for more information.

Project Meetings Calendar

The project meetings calendar is set up in ZeroW Project Teams Area, channel General, tab [Project Meetings Calendar](#). It aims to provide visibility on the regular (scheduled) project operative meetings, including PSG meetings, WP progress meetings. Council of Partners and External Advisory Board meetings will also be written in the calendar when those are scheduled.

Mailing lists

To provide a means for easy communication within the individual WPs delivery teams and the PSG members, the Project Coordinator has set up the following mailing lists:

ZeroW PSG	ZeroW_PSG@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP1	ZeroW_WP1@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP10	ZeroW_WP10@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP2	ZeroW_WP2@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP3	ZeroW_WP3@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP4	ZeroW_WP4@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP5	ZeroW_WP5@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP6	ZeroW_WP6@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP7	ZeroW_WP7@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP8	ZeroW_WP8@inlecomsystems.com
ZeroW WP9	ZeroW_WP9@inlecomsystems.com

The addressees of each of those lists can be found (and updated if required) in the project [Contact List](#).

Note: The WP Leads should maintain the WP Lists contact up to date and inform the PC about any changes required either through email or through comment against the contact details, including the date of the change request to allow for traceability of the information.

ZeroW Partners Newsletter (Internal newsletter)

The Project Coordinator has organised the delivery of the internal project newsletter as an effective communication mechanism with all the partners. The Newsletter is

sent to all contacts included in the Project Partners sheet in the ZeroW [Contact Sheet](#).

The internal newsletter includes information regarding the project progress, important decisions, results and lessons learnt. It will not have a regular schedule, rather it will be sent when there is content of interest.

The distributed newsletters are stored in the ZeroW Project Teams area, channel WP11, Tab Files, Folder Internal Comms, [Newsletters](#).

Collaborative workspace – ZeroW Project MS Teams Area

Figure 18 ZeroW Project Teams Area

Main principles of organisation

The Coordinator has set-up a collaborative workspace for the ZeroW Consortium in MS Teams. Each partner has been provided with access to the Project Teams Area and can actively contribute to the communication and content generation.

Changes to the members of the ZeroW Project Teams Area are made only by the Coordinator on request by the respective Partner. This includes adding new members and deleting members.

When a new member is added, the respective person receives an email invitation to join the ZeroW Project Team and a link.

Note: *If you or any of your colleagues experience issues with logging in the ZeroW Project Team area, please inform the Coordinator immediately!*

The project team members can download and upload document, edit documents directly in the Teams area, either using the web interface or through the desktop application. Multiple members can work on the same document simultaneously,

making the collaborative working easier and more efficient and bridging the gaps between the geographically dispersed partners.

Additionally, the Team members can create posts, comment/respond on posts in the individual channels. The posts will be visible to all Team members. When there is a new post in a channel, the channel name font changes to **bold** (see Figure 19). However, no specific notification about the post will be sent to the Team members.

Figure 19 MS Teams view: New post in Channel WP11 as seen by all Team members

In order to increase the visibility to the post, the members can mention another member (using **@[member username]**) and use Tags. In this case, the mentioned members only will receive notification in their Activity tab on the left of the application screen (see Figure 20 and Figure 21). The rest of the Team members will only see that there is a new message (channel name in bold), but no notification in their Activity tab (see Figure 19).

Figure 20 MS Teams view: Notification for new post mention, as seen by the Teams member that is mentioned or tagged in a post

Figure 21 Notification view in the Activity tab

The Coordinator has created a tag for each member to attribute him to the respective partner. In this case, for example, if one wants to notify all the ICP team members, they should mention **@ICP** in the respective post. When this is done, the members with tag ICP will receive notification in their Activity tab in the MS Teams application (see Figure 20 and Figure 21).

The Coordinator has set the channel structure of the ZeroW Project Teams Area. The members cannot create new/delete existing channels. Should a Partner need a new channel to be created, he/she needs to request that from the Coordinator.

Note: Only 11 channels are originally visible by the Team members. The rest of the channels are hidden. In order to see them, each member have to make them visible one by one. This is a system limitation (see Figure 22).

Figure 22 System limitation for auto-show channels in a team

In order to make the hidden channels visible, click on the chevron to the right of the hidden channels and select the channel(s) you want to unhide (see Figure 23).

Figure 23 Unhide channels

Communication channels

Channels are dedicated sections within a team to keep conversations organized by specific topics. The Channels are the places where conversations happen and where the work actually gets done⁵.

The ZeroW Project Team Area is composed of 14 channels, based on the project work organisation and the auditorium for the specific information, published in the respective channel. With one exception, all of the ZeroW Project Team channels are open for all team members, i.e. all partners have access to the information provided, the files located in the respective channel and can participate in the discussions to the respective channel chat.

⁵ Source <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoftteams/teams-channels-overview>

There is one private channel, dedicated specifically for the commercially sensitive information that might be shared with WP7 as part of the IPR management and protection task. Access to this area have only the ICP employees.

The organisational structure of the channels and their intended purpose, primary audience and access level are provided in the following table.

Channel Name	Description	Intended primary audience	Access rights
General	Tabs for Project plan, Project Meetings calendar, ZeroW Contact List. Files stored: Contractual document (GA, CA, NDAs); Document templates; Logos; images; videos; Deliverable final versions repository; Periodic reporting.	All Teams members	All Teams members
Project Governance (Bodies and Meetings)	Communication and documents related to structuring and functioning of the Project Council of Partners (PCP) and the Project Steering Group (PSG). Project Meetings information to be stored here as well.	PSG members and All Partners	All Teams members
WP01 - Modelling FLW Economics from F2F (WU)	Collaborative workspace for delivering of the respective WP. All WP deliverables, shared documents, meeting related files, planning information and posts related to WP should be included here.	Partners delivering the respective WP, partners collaborating with the respective WP	All Teams members
WP02 - FLW Digitalisation Service Portfolio (TNO)			
WP03 - Systemic Innovation Support Tools (WIT)			
WP04 - Systemic Innovation Demonstration (BIOS)			
WP05 - Systemic Innovation Assessment (DIGI)			
WP06 - Fostering SI, Capacity Building (EV-ILVO)			
WP07 - Exploitation, Commercialisation (ICP)			
WP08 - Policy Recommendations (SAFE)			
WP09 - Cooperation with EC Initiatives (ICLEI)			
WP10 - Dissemination and Communication (FBCD)			
WP11 - Project Management			
WP7 ICP Private	Dedicated space for confidential information in relation to IPR management and protection	WP7 Lead and ICP T7.4 delivery team	ICP team members only

The documentation and communication for the individual work packages is located in the respective WP channel.

Additionally, the General channel contains information of interest to the entire consortium, including GA, CA, document templates, logos and other useful information. You may find more detailed information in section *File repository structure*.

The Project Governance channel contains information, communication and files, related to the functioning of the project management bodies – the CoP and PSG, including decisions, meeting agendas, presentations, minutes, etc.

File repository structure

The ZeroW project files are stored on Inlecom SharePoint server. MS Teams provides access interface to them. The organisation of the repository follows the structure of the channels, e.g. the files, related to the delivery of each WP are located in the respective WP channel, tab Files.

The coordinator has created an initial file structure in each **WP file folder** that includes subfolders for:

- Deliverables – the WP final versions of the deliverables should be stored here, in Word (or another editable format) and PDF.
- Meetings and Minutes – agendas, presentations, recording, minutes, attendance lists for the meeting organised in relation to the delivery of the WP.
- Tasks – work in progress documents/deliverables, task planning information etc.

The WP Lead and team can adapt the file structure for their needs. **The WP Lead has the responsibility to maintain the WP channel and WP documentation up to date.**

***Note:** The use of the **Deliverables** and **Meetings and Minutes** subfolders is mandatory! They provide the Coordinator and the rest of the team with visibility on the project progress and the completed deliverables.*

The Coordinator will copy the completed deliverables in the General channel, where there is a dedicated folder for the final version of the deliverables for the entire project.

The **General** file folder has the following structure:

- Contact List – contains the latest version of the ZeroW project contact list. The superseded versions are collated in a subfolder Old versions and drafts.
- Contractual documents, with subfolders:
 - Agreements – contains the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement
 - NDAs & Support Letters – repository for the received support letters and the NDAs signed in relation to the project. **It is a responsibility**

of the partners to review the content of this subfolder regularly to stay in touch with the confidentiality agreements with other projects, initiatives and organisations.

- Original application – contains the 3 files submitted as original proposal and the Evaluation Summary Report.

Quick access: The Tabs in the General Channel provide a quick access to important project files:

- The **ZeroW project plan**: an Excel file, containing the WBS, Gantt chart, RACI matrix and efforts per task, start-end dates and duration. Separate worksheet for the Deliverables and integrated quality management plan.
- The **ZeroW project calendar** provides a view of the CoP, PSG and individual WP meetings. It is maintained by the Coordinator based on the information, provided by the WP leads.
- The **ZeroW Contact List**: an Excel file, containing the current information about the ZeroW partners contact details. For more information, please see section Contact list and maintenance.

The **Project Governance (Bodies and Meetings)** file repository has the following structure:

- External Advisory Board – the documents related with the functioning of the EAB will be stored here.
- Kick-off Meeting – includes the documents related to the preparation and delivery of the ZeroW project kick-off meeting
 - Attendance List – automatically generated attendees list, produced by MS Teams based on the members, logged in the Kick-off virtual meeting.
 - Kick-off Meeting Presentations – the PowerPoint/PDF files for the WP presentations, SILLs presentations, Coordinator presentation, General project overview presentation, EC Policy Officer, Project Officer and Financial Officer presentations.
 - Kick-off Meeting Recordings – contains the recording of the Kick-off meeting sessions.
 - Minutes – the file with the summary of actions and decisions discussed during the KoM.
 - Pre-kick-off technical workshop - includes the documents related to the preparation and delivery of the preparatory technical workshop.
- Project Council of Partners
 - Decisions – log of the CoP decisions
 - Meetings – preparatory documents, agendas, presentations, recordings, minutes organised in subfolders for each meeting.
- Project Steering Group

- Decisions – log of the CoP decisions
- Meetings – preparatory documents, agendas, presentations, recordings, minutes organised in subfolders for each meeting.

Conflicts resolution

In the context of our multilateral project collaboration, encompassing 46 partners and 3 linked entities, 11 work packages, and 9 systemic innovations living labs and demonstrators, we recognise the importance of pre-emptively mitigating conflicts to ensure the smooth progression of our ambitious project. To this end, ZeroW project policy prioritises the creation of conditions that inherently reduce the likelihood of conflicts. This is achieved by applying a rigorous risk management process, proactively identifying potential areas of conflict, and implementing strategies to address these risks before they escalate into conflicts (see section [RISK MANAGEMENT PLAN](#)).

The current section outlines a structured conflict resolution process, designed to manage and resolve conflicts in the rare instances they arise. Despite the preventative measures, we acknowledge that conflicts may still occur due to the complex and dynamic nature of our project. Therefore, this procedure provides a clear and effective mechanism for resolving disputes, ensuring that ZeroW ambitious objectives and impacts are not hindered by unresolved issues.

Key Contacts

Technical Contacts: Each partner organisation has designated technical contacts, who are included in the project's Contact List.

Escalation Contacts: Each partner must appoint an Escalation Contact, responsible for handling unresolved issues at a higher organizational level. This information should be appended to the project's Contact List.

Conflict Resolution Process

The process follows a hierarchical escalation model:

Table 42 Conflict resolution process steps

Level	Action	Description	Documentation
1. Task Level	Initial Discussion	Issues are first addressed at the task level among the technical contacts of the collaborating partners.	Document discussions and attempted resolutions.
	Resolution Attempt	Efforts to solve the issue through discussion, negotiation, and mutual agreement.	
2. WP Level	Escalation Trigger	If unresolved at the task level, the issue is escalated to the respective Work Package level.	Document escalation and resolution attempts.
	WP Leader Involvement	WP Leader facilitates further discussions and attempts to resolve the issue.	
3. Coordinator Level	Second Escalation	If still unresolved at WP level, the issue is escalated to the Project Coordinator.	Comprehensive documentation of actions and decisions.
	Coordinator's Intervention	Coordinator assesses the issue, involving relevant stakeholders, and attempts to find a resolution.	
4. Project Steering Group Level	Final Escalation	If unresolved by Coordinator, it is brought to the Project Steering Group.	Document decisions and outcomes.
	Steering Group Deliberation	The group deliberates on the issue, considering the project's broader objectives and impacts.	
	Decision Making	A decision by the Steering Group is final and binding within the scope of project collaboration.	
5. Consortium Agreement	Dispute Resolution	Conflicts that defy resolution through the above steps are handled as per the Consortium Agreement.	Document the invocation of the dispute resolution provision.

When the conflict is related to individual partner performance issues, the following actions should be performed:

Table 43 Performance issues resolution steps

Level	Action	Description	Documentation
Individual Partner Performance Issues	Initial Handling	Address issues like quality of work, late deliveries, and interpersonal conflicts within the delivery team.	Document discussions and resolutions.
	Internal Escalation	If unresolved, escalate within the respective partner organization, following their internal protocols.	Document internal escalation and outcomes.

Documentation and Transparency

All stages of conflict resolution should be properly documented, maintaining a clear record of discussions, decisions, and outcomes. A template to support his process in created and included in [ANNEX III: CONFLICT RESOLUTION RECORD DOCUMENT TEMPLATE](#)

Transparency and open communication are key, ensuring all involved parties are informed and engaged throughout the process.

This conflict resolution procedure is designed to facilitate a harmonious and efficient collaborative environment, essential for achieving the project's ambitious objectives. It underscores the importance of structured communication and escalation to ensure all conflicts are addressed promptly and effectively.

7. Stakeholder Management Plan

Link to deliverable D9.1 Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement.

8. Annex I: ZeroW high-level Gantt chart

9. Annex II: Guide for reporting of D&C activities

Step 1

Click the link <https://podio.com/webforms/27010388/2068492>

Step 2

Write the name or topic of the activity like “Presentation at Global Food Waste Conference 2022”, “LinkedIn post about ZeroW project kick off meeting”, etc. (see screenshot 1).

podio.com/webforms/27010388/2068492

rks M Merlin Learn basic Chinese... Free website creation (intet emne) - loukr... http://www.google...

D&C Reporting ZeroW

Please provide documentation for your D&C activities in the ZeroW project in this webform. If you experience any technical issues, please contact Louise Krogh Johnson, lkj@foodbiocluster.dk

Name or topic of activity *

Presentation at Global Food Waste Conference 2022

Responsible ZeroW partner *

FBCD A/S

Contact person *

Louise Krogh Johnson

Email *

Andet lkj@foodbiocluster.dk

Tilføj en til

Screenshot 1

Step 3

Type in your organization with the full name or your organisation’s abbreviation in the project and enter your name and e-mail. (Please ignore the ‘Andet’ and ‘Tilføj en til’ fields).

Step 4

Add other partners involved in the activity, if any (see screenshot 2).

Contributing ZeroW partners (if applicable)

x Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP)

Screenshot 2

Step 5

Choose the right category for the activity (see screenshot 3).

Type of D&C activity *

A screenshot of a dropdown menu titled "Type of D&C activity *". The menu is open, showing several options. The top option is "2A - Presentations in conferences, seminars, trade shows, exhibitions. Face-to-face meetings (Industry)", which is highlighted in light blue. Below it are "2B Articles and features in industry magazines (Industry)", "2C Promotion through professional organisations and networks (Industry)", and "2D Scale up regional workshops (Industry)". At the bottom of the list is "3A Direct contacts, personal invitations, conferences & other events (Policy programme, brochure, photos, etc.) or a link." The dropdown arrow is visible on the right side of the menu.

Screenshot 3

OBS: We have added an option called "Alternative D&C activities where the project was promoted (not included in grant agreement targets)" but be aware that organizing alternative D&C events must be cleared with FBCD and Inlecom in advance.

Step 6

Add the date of the activity.

Step 7

Provide a brief description of the activity that clarifies the context.

Example:

Description of activity *

Describe the activity and how the ZeroW project was promoted.

DOCUMENTATION MUST BE PROVIDED in the form of an attachment (e.g. a programme, brochure, photos, etc.) or a link.

FBCD was invited to give a presentation about the ZeroW project at Global Food Waste Conference 2022. The conference was virtual and had approx. 300 participants mainly from industry.

Louise Krogh Johnson gave a 15 minute presentation about SILL 7

Screenshot 4

Step 8

Attach documentation for the activity (see screenshot 5). In the example above you could attach photos or screenshots from the presentation and the PowerPoint slides (pdf).

Files are attached with the use of the buttons below (unfortunately in Danish only):

'Bilag' = Attachment

'Vælg fil' = Select file

'Tilføj en til' = Add another file

Bilag

Screenshot 5

Step 9

Add link for further documentation.

It could be to the event page, an online programme, a social media post, or whatever is relevant. It may also be a screenshot from your calendar or an email exchange to document a meeting, a pdf-version of a poster, a scientific article, and so on.

Step 10

Submit by clicking "Send"

FBCD will check all submissions continuously. If you don't hear anything, the submitted activity is approved and will be included in the next project report. If something is missing or there are questions about the content, you will hear from us.

If you experience technical problems, please contact dissemination manager Louise Krogh Johnson (lkj@foodbiocluster.dk).

10. Annex III: Conflict Resolution Record Document Template

Purpose

The Conflict Resolution Record serves as a centralised and structured way to record and track all conflicts, their resolution attempts, and outcomes within the project. This document will facilitate transparency, accountability, and effective communication among project partners.

Structure of the Document

Conflict Resolution Record

Project Acronym ZeroW **Grant Agreement No** 101036388

Document	Conflict Resolution Record
Date of Creation	
Version Number	
Author	

Conflict Identification

Conflict ID: [Unique identifier for each conflict]

Date of Creation	
Date Reported	
Reported By	[Name and organization of the person who reported the conflict]
Involved Parties	[Names and organizations of all parties involved in the conflict]

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
VX.X	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[Text]	[Initials]

Conflict Description

- **Brief Description:** A concise description of the conflict.
- **Work Package/Lab Involved:** Identify the specific work package or lab related to the conflict.
- **Impact Assessment:** Brief analysis of how the conflict impacts project goals, timelines, or relations.

Resolution Attempts

1. Task Level Attempt:

- **Date:** When the resolution was attempted at the task level.
- **Details:** Actions taken and discussions held.
- **Outcome:** Result of the task level resolution attempt.

2. WP Level Attempt:

- Date
- Details
- Outcome

3. Coordinator Level Attempt:

- Date
- Details
- Outcome

4. Steering Group Level Attempt:

- Date
- Details
- Outcome

Final Resolution

- **Resolution Details:** Detailed description of the final resolution.
- **Resolution Date**
- **Agreed By:** Names and signatures of parties agreeing to the resolution.

Follow-up Actions

- **Actions Required:** Specific actions required to implement the resolution.
- **Responsible Parties:** Who is responsible for carrying out these actions.

- Deadline for Actions:

Review and Closure

- Review Date: When the resolution's effectiveness is to be reviewed.
- Closure Confirmation: Confirmation that the conflict has been resolved and the case is closed.
- Closed By: Name and signature of the person closing the conflict case.

Attachments

- Supporting Documents: Any relevant emails, meeting notes, or other documents.

Responsibility for Document Maintenance

The document should be maintained by a designated Project Administrator or Conflict Resolution Officer, named as "Author" on the Documents header page.

They are responsible for updating the document as conflicts progress through resolution stages and ensuring its accuracy and confidentiality.

Access and Confidentiality

Access to the document should be controlled and limited to relevant parties to maintain confidentiality.

Summary reports can be generated for broader distribution among the project partners, omitting sensitive details.

Updating and Review

The document should be reviewed regularly to ensure it is up-to-date and accurately reflects the status of conflicts within the project.

Revisions to the document should be tracked through version numbers and change logs.